

Monitoring zum englischsprachigen Forschungsstand „Sexuelle Gewalt in pädagogischen Kontexten“

BIBLIOGRAPHIE, NUMMER 2

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HENNINGSEN

GEFÖRDERT VOM

Bundesministerium
für Bildung
und Forschung

Hintergrund

Dieses Monitoring dient in erster Linie den Forscher_innen innerhalb der BMBF-Förderlinie „Sexualisierte Gewalt gegen Kinder und Jugendliche in pädagogischen Kontexten“, einen strukturierten sowie konzentrierten Zugang zu relevanten englischsprachigen Publikationen zu erhalten. Darüber hinaus profitieren weitere Forscher_innen und Studierende, aber auch pädagogische Fachkräfte von thematischen Anschlussstellen der Literatursammlung. Mit dieser Bibliographie ist der Publikationszeitraum von 2010 bis 2018 abgedeckt.

Schwerpunktmäßig erfasst das Monitoring den Ausschnitt „sexuelle Gewalt in pädagogischen Kontexten“ und integriert flankierende grundsätzliche Zusammenhänge von Gewalt und Sexualität. Relevante Unterthemen wurden anhand inhaltlicher Clusterungen des Forschungsnetzwerks herausgearbeitet, d.h. die Recherche konzentriert sich auf die *soziale Rahmung von sexueller Gewalt*, die *organisationalen Strukturen und Kulturen*, die *Qualifizierung von Fachkräften*, *Präventionsprogramme für Adressat_innen* sowie *Disclosure*.¹ Da aber auch sexuelle Gewalt in familialen und Peerbeziehungen eine Auswirkung auf die pädagogische Arbeit haben und im Laufe der Literaturrecherche sich als wichtige Forschungs- und Publikationsthemen herausstellten, werden sie in diesem Monitoring ebenfalls berücksichtigt.

Auswahl der Titel

Der Ausschnitt des Monitorings weist eine immense Themenbreite auf: Wegen der Inter- und Multidisziplinarität ist eine vollständige Darstellung aller relevanten Veröffentlichungen nicht möglich. Die Disziplinen und teilweise unabhängigen Netzwerke, die sich mit Gewalt und Sexualität in pädagogischen Kontexten befassen, verhindern eine vollständige systematische Literaturreview (Tranfield *et al.* 2003: 215). Für einen möglichst repräsentativen Überblick wurde deswegen eine zielgerichtete, geschichtete Zufallsauswahl getroffen, die sich auf die aktuellen Diskurse und Publikationen seit 2010 – dem Beginn der öffentlichen, politischen und pädagogischen Auf- und Bearbeitung von Missbrauchsfällen in pädagogischen Institutionen – konzentriert. Zur Qualitätssicherung und wegen der zu erwartenden Reichweite sowie des damit zusammenhängenden Einflusses wurde beschlossen, sich auf peer-reviewte Zeitschriftenartikel und, um einer einseitigen Repräsentation des Forschungsfeldes durch Artikel vorzubeugen (Hicks 2005), Monographien und Sammelbände namhafter Verlage zu konzentrieren.

Systematische Literaturreviews werden für gewöhnlich anhand von Schlagwortsuche in ausgewählten Datenbanken durchgeführt (Boell & Cecez-Kecmanovic 2010: 134f.; Okoli & Schabram 2010). Wegen der Vielfalt an relevanten Schlagwörtern einerseits und der geringen Präzision dieses Vorgehens (Boell & Cecez-Kecmanovic 2010: 132) – man denke beispielsweise an die fehlerhaft ausgewählten Artikel zu „sex*“, die sich ausschließlich auf Geschlechterunterschiede beziehen – kommt diese Methode nicht in Frage. Alternativ wird mit einer Konzentration auf *core journals* gearbeitet, ausgehend von Bradfords Gesetz, dass Themen sich nicht gleichmäßig auf alle Zeitschriften verteilen, sondern in einzelnen verstärkt anzufinden sind (Bradford 1947; Brookes 1977). Dieses Vorgehen erlaubt eine natürliche Begrenzung durch die Vorauswahl der Zeitschriften (Alavi & Carlson 1992; Okoli & Schabram 2010). Da wir aber nicht nur an Forschungserkenntnissen interessiert sind, sondern auch daran, wie die Auseinandersetzung mit sexueller Gewalt, Gewalt und Sexualität in pädagogischen Kontexten in den verschiedenen Disziplinen stattfindet, wie sich also das Forschungsfeld darstellt und entwickelt, ist eine ausschließliche Fokussierung auf etwaige Hauptzeitschriften ebenfalls nicht optimal. Um einen repräsentativen Einblick in das englischsprachige Forschungsfeld „sexuelle Gewalt in pädagogischen

¹ Beiträge, die die „Entwicklung akademischer Curricula“ unterstützen könnten, wurden ebenfalls der Qualifizierung von Fachkräften zugeordnet.

Kontexten“ zu bieten und seine Verteilung, nehmen wir deshalb neben thematischen Zeitschriften auch disziplinübergreifend Standardwerke in den Blick.

Die Auswahl der Zeitschriftenartikel erfolgte geschichtet mit einer zielgerichteten Zufallsauswahl von 25 Zeitschriften, die anschließend nach relevanten Artikeln durchsucht wurden. Bei der Auswahl der Zeitschriften, die über *Google Scholar Metrics*, *Scimano Journal and County Rank* und *SAGE Publishing* sowie Empfehlungen von einschlägigen Fachbereichen identifiziert wurden, spielten vier Kriterien eine Rolle. *Erstens* war es ein Anliegen, sowohl relevante Disziplinen zu berücksichtigen (also Zeitschriften der Erziehungswissenschaften, Psychologie und Gesundheitswissenschaften sowie Sozialwissenschaften) als auch einschlägige Fachzeitschriften der Bereiche Sexualität, sexuelle Gewalt, Kindesmisshandlung und Zeitschriften zu empirischer Forschung einzubeziehen. *Zweitens* wurden Zeitschriften bevorzugt, die eine hohe Trefferquote bei der Suche nach Schlagwörtern ergaben.² *Als drittes Kriterium* galt der h5-Index, also die Zitierhäufigkeit,³ und *viertens* wurde schließlich der Ort der Herausgeberschaft berücksichtigt. Veröffentlichungen aus dem globalen Norden wurden dabei bevorzugt, weil von besseren Vergleichsmöglichkeiten zum deutschen Kontext ausgegangen wird. Um die Überrepräsentation der USA nach dieser Auswahl auszugleichen, wurden Zeitschriften bevorzugt, die in Europa, Kanada oder Australien/Neuseeland herausgegeben wurden. Insgesamt ergab sich eine Summe von 131 Zeitschriften, sodass eine engere Auswahl in Form einer geschichteten Zufallsstichprobe getroffen wurde, die die Repräsentation der Disziplinen und Erscheinungsorte widerspiegelt.

Zeitschrift	Erscheinungsort	h5-Index	ISSN
Archives of Sexual Behavior*	Kanada	44	0004-0002
British Journal of Social Work	Großbritannien	33	0045-3102
Child Abuse & Neglect*	Kanada	39	0145-2134
Child Abuse Review	Großbritannien	17	09529136
Childhood	Norwegen	24	0907-5682
Children and Youth Services Review*	USA	44	01907409
Culture, Health & Sexuality*	Australien	27	1464-5351
Feminism & Psychology	Neuseeland	20	0959-3535
Gender & Society	USA	31	0891-2432
Gender and Education	Großbritannien	22	0954-0253
Journal of Adolescence*	USA	46	0140-1971
Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry	Großbritannien	71	1469-7610
Journal of Child Sexual Abuse*	USA	17	1053-8712
Journal of Curriculum Studies	Österreich	20	1366-5839

² Die Liste der Schlagwörter kann bei Interesse eingesehen werden.

³ Der Impact-Faktor ist zwar ein umstrittenes Kriterium in den Sozialwissenschaften, bietet aber eine Annäherung an die Identifikation einflussreicher Zeitschriften (Furr 2014; Sellers *et al.* 2014).

Journal of Sexual Aggression*	Australien	15	1355-2600
Journal of Sex Research*	Großbritannien	36	1559-8519
Journal of Youth and Adolescence*	USA	48	0047-2891
Men and Masculinities	USA	20	1097184X
Pedagogy, Culture & Society	Großbritannien	15	1468-1366
Qualitative Research	International	33	1468-7941
Research in Developmental Disabilities	Großbritannien	48	0891-4222
Sex Education*	Großbritannien	17	1472-0825
Sexuality and Disability	USA	16	0146-1044
Sexuality Research and Social Policy*	USA	18	1868-9884
Teaching and Teacher Education	Australien	51	0742051X

Tabelle 1: Auswahl der berücksichtigten Zeitschriften.

Um die für den Themenkomplex „sexuelle Gewalt, Gewalt und Sexualität in pädagogischen Kontexten“ relevanten Artikel aus den ausgewählten Zeitschriften zu identifizieren, wurden sämtliche Aufsatztitel in allen Ausgaben ab 2010 durchgesehen. Anschließend erfolgte auch hier eine Schlagwortsuche, um sicherzugehen, dass keine Artikel übersehen wurden. Bei Zeitschriften mit einer relevanten Artikelanzahl von über zehn pro Jahr wurde aus diesen eine Zufallsstichprobe ausgewählt.⁴ Insgesamt ergab sich damit eine Zahl von 1.056 Artikeln.

Die Auswahl der Bücher – Monographien und Sammelbände - erfolgte über die Universitätsverlage der 50 weltweit besten Universitäten (Times Higher Education Ranking 2016/2017), sowie *SAGE Publications* und *Routledge* als weitere große akademischen Verlage, die in stichprobenartigen Schlagwortsuchen bei der digitalen Bibliothek *WorldCat* am häufigsten auftauchten. Bei den Universitätsverlagen wurde wie bei der Artikelauswahl vorgegangen und die gesamten Publikationen seit 2010 durchgesehen. Bei *SAGE Publications* und *Routledge* wurde mit Schlagwörtern gesucht. Aus dieser Buchsammlung wurden anhand der o.g. Kriterien 67 Monographien und 31 Sammelbände ausgewählt.

⁴ In der Liste sind diese Zeitschriften mit einem * gekennzeichnet.

- 1. Datenbanken: *Google Scholar Metrics*; *Scimano Journal and County Rank*; *SAGE Publishing*
- 2. Fachbereichsempfehlungen: McGill Institute für Gender, Sexuality and Feminist Studies; Northeastern University's Women's, Gender, and Sexuality Studies Programme
- 3. Verlage: der 50 besten Universitäten und mit hoher Trefferquote bei *Google Books* und *SAGE Publishing*
- 4. Kriterien-geleitete Auswahl für Zeitschriften
 - Treffer Schlagwörter
 - Impact-Faktor
 - Ort Herausgeberschaft
 - Gleichmäßige Verteilung Disziplinen und Themen

- 1. Durchsehen jeder Ausgabe von 2010 bis 2017
- 2. Entscheidung anhand von Titel und ggf. Abstract
- 3. Kontrolle durch anschließende Schlagwortsuche
- 4. Zufallsauswahl bei Zeitschriften mit mehr als 10 relevanten Artikeln pro Jahr

- 1. Primäre Einordnung durch Cluster des Forschungsnetzwerks
- 2. Hermeneutischer Zirkel des Nachjustierens: weitere Kategorien ergänzt, Bildung von Subkategorien, Ausschluss von vernachlässigbaren Kategorien
- 3. Manuelle Zuteilung von Schlagwörtern, kontinuierlich weiterentwickelt
- 4. Aussortierung von Artikeln, die wider Erwarten irrelevant sind

Abbildung 1: Vorgehen bei der Recherche nach Zeitschriftenartikeln und Büchern.

Kategorisierung und Einordnung der Titel

Die anschließende Strukturierung der Veröffentlichungen orientierte sich an den oben erwähnten Clustern des Forschungsnetzwerks – die *soziale Rahmung*, die *organisationalen Strukturen und Kulturen*, die *Qualifizierung von Fachkräften*, *Präventionsprogramme für Adressat_innen* sowie *Disclosure* und *Entwicklung akademischer Curricula* – wurde jedoch im Laufe der Recherche induktiv angepasst, erweitert und mit Unterkategorien versehen. Die Titel wurden anhand ihrer Abstracts oder Einleitungen diesen Kategorien zugeordnet; Mehrfachkategorien waren möglich.

1. Soziale Rahmung
 - 1.1. Policies und politische Ebene
 - 1.2. Weiterführende Diskurse rund um Sexualität, Gewalt, sexuelle Gewalt und pädagogische Arbeit
 - 1.3. Gebrauch von Medien (auch soziale/neue) und Technologie
 - 1.4. Soziale Gruppen und Diskriminierung
 - 1.4.1. Geschlechterrollen und Sexismus
 - 1.4.2. Sexuelle Orientierung und geschlechtliche Identität; Homo-, Bi- und Transfeindlichkeit
 - 1.4.3. Schichtenzugehörigkeit und Klassismus
 - 1.4.4. Ethnizität und Rassismus
 - 1.4.5. Religionszugehörigkeit und -feindlichkeit
 - 1.4.6. Behinderungen und Ableismus
2. Institutioneller Kontext
 - 2.1. Institutionelle Dynamiken (inkl. Richtlinien auf Einrichtungsebene)

- 2.2. Einrichtungstypen
 - 2.2.1. Kindertagesstätte
 - 2.2.2. Grundschule
 - 2.2.3. Weiterführende Schule
 - 2.2.4. Hochschule
 - 2.2.5. Förderschule
 - 2.2.6. Kinder- und Jugendhilfe
 - 2.2.7. Sonstiges (Jugendzentrum, Kirche, Justizvollzugsanstalt, Jugendamt)
- 3. Pädagogischer Fokus
 - 3.1. Sexualpädagogik
 - 3.2. Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention
- 4. Fachkräfte (Qualifizierung, Professionalisierung, ihre Einstellungen zu Sexualität und sexueller Gewalt und Umgang damit)
 - 4.1. Innerhalb von Einrichtungen
 - 4.2. Externe
 - 4.3. Peer Education
- 5. Adressat_innen
 - 5.1. Kinder
 - 5.2. Jugendliche
 - 5.3. Eltern und Familien
- 6. Formen und Auswirkungen der Gewalt
 - 6.1. Täter*in
 - 6.1.1. Peer
 - 6.1.2. Erwachsene
 - 6.2. Art
 - 6.2.1. Sexuelle Belästigung
 - 6.2.2. Sexueller Kindesmissbrauch
 - 6.2.3. Vergewaltigung
 - 6.2.4. Übergriff
 - 6.2.5. Diskriminierung
 - 6.3. Folgen
 - 6.3.1. Negativ (u.a. Reviktimisierung, Täter_innenschaft, PTBS)
 - 6.3.3. Coping, Resilienz, Posttraumatisches Wachstum
 - 6.3.4. Disclosure
- 7. Rolle von Sexualität
 - 7.1. Beziehungsgestaltung
 - 7.2. Sexuelle Selbstbestimmung
 - 7.3. Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Darüber hinaus wurde den Publikationen Schlagwörter zugeordnet, die sich z.T. aus den von den Verlagen bereits vorgesehenen Schlagwörtern ergaben und im Laufe der Recherche ergänzt und synthetisiert wurden. Auch hier wurden mehrere Schlagwörter vergeben.

Literatur

Alavi, Maryam; Carlson, Patricia (1992): A review of MIS research and disciplinary development. In: *Journal of Management Information Systems* 8 (4), S. 45–62.

Boell, Sebastian K.; Cecez-Kecmanovic, Dubravka (2014): A hermeneutic approach for conducting literature reviews and literature searches. In: *Communications of the Association for Information Systems* 34 (12), S. 257–286.

- Bradford, Samuel C. (1947): Complete Documentation. In: *Nature* 159 (4029), S. 105–106.
- Brookes, Bertram C. (1977): Theory of the Bradford Law. In: *Journal of Documentation* 33 (3), S. 180–209.
- Furr, Allen L. (1995): The Relative Influence of Social Work Journals. In: *Journal of Social Work Education* 31 (1), S. 38–45.
- Hicks, Diana (2005): The Four Literatures of Social Science. In: Henk F. Moed, Wolfgang Gl?nzel und Ulrich Schmoch (Hg.): *Handbook of Quantitative Science and Technology Research*. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers, S. 473–496.
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- Sellers, Sherrill L.; Mathiesen, Sally G.; Perry, Robin; Smith, Thomas (2004): Evaluation of Social Work Journal Quality. Citation versus Reputation Approaches. In: *Journal of Social Work Education* 40 (1), S. 143–160.
- Tranfield, David; Denyer, David; Smart, Palminder (2003): Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence-Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review. In: *British Journal of Management* 14 (3), S. 207–222.

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Aktuelle Beiträge

1. 2018

Abajobir, Amanuel A.; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail; Strathearn, Lane; Najman, Jake M. (2018):

Risky Sexual Behaviors and Pregnancy Outcomes in Young Adulthood Following Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment: Findings From a Prospective Birth Cohort Study.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (1), S. 106–119. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1368975.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Kinder // children; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; Vernachlässigung // neglect

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Airton, Lee (2018):

The de/politicization of pronouns. Implications of the No Big Deal Campaign for gender-expansive educational policy and practice.

In: *Gender and Education* 30 (6), S. 790–810. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2018.1483489.

Schlagwörter:

Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kanada // Canada; Medien // media; Medienanalyse // media analysis; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Politik // politics; queer // queer; Soziale Medien // social media; Theorie // theory; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Alkhalailah, Duna; Hayford, Sarah R.; Norris, Alison H.; Gallo, Maria F. (2018):

Prevalence and attitudes on female genital mutilation/cutting in Egypt since criminalisation in 2008.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 20 (2), S. 173–182. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2017.1337927.

Schlagwörter:

Ägypten // Egypt; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Genitalbeschneidung // Genital cutting; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Gesundheit // health; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Heirat // marriage; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Muslimische Länder // Muslim countries; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Alzoubi, Fatmeh Ahmad; Ali, Reem Ahmad; Flah, Intesar Hussein; Alnatour, Ahlam (2018):

Mothers' knowledge & perception about child sexual abuse in Jordan.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 75, S. 149–158. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.06.006.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jordanien // Jordan; Muslimische Länder // Muslim countries; Mutter // mother; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Asamoah, Benedict Opong; Agardh, Anette (2018):

Individual- and Family-Level Determinants of Risky Sexual Behavior Among Swedish- and Foreign-Born Young Adults 18-30 Years of Age, Residing in Skåne, Sweden.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (2), S. 517–528. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-017-0978-5.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Erwachsene // adults; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schweden // Sweden; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Atteberry-Ash, Brittanie; Woodford, Michael R. (2018):

Support for Policy Protecting LGBT Student Athletes among Heterosexual Students Participating in Club and Intercollegiate Sports.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 151–162. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0283-z.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Schutz // protection; Sport // sports; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; trans*ident // trans*; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Axford, Nick; Berry, Vashti (2018):

Perfect Bedfellows. Why Early Intervention Can Play a Critical Role in Protecting Children—A Response to Featherstone et al. (2014) ‘A Marriage Made in Hell: Child Protection Meets Early Intervention’.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 48 (1), S. 254–273. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcx003.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Intervention // intervention; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Kommentar // commentary; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Azzopardi, Corry; Alaggia, Ramona; Fallon, Barbara (2018):

From Freud to Feminism. Gendered Constructions of Blame Across Theories of Child Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (3), S. 254–275. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1390717.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Ehtik // ethics; Feminismus // feminism; Geschlecht // gender; Kanada // Canada; Mutter // mother; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungsethik // research ethics; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jungen // boys; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Geschlecht // gender; Intimität // intimacy; Konsens // consent; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Maguin, Eugene; Bruns, Anne E. (2018):

Who Wears the Pants. The Implications of Gender and Power for Youth Heterosexual Relationships.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (1), S. 7–20. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1276881.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Macht // power; Nordamerika // North America; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Being an 'adolescent'. The consequences of gendered risks for young people in rural Uganda.

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Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gesundheit // health; Intervention // intervention; Jugend // youth; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Uganda // Uganda

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Billard, Thomas J. (2018):

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Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Methodologie // methodology; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Kinder // children; Literaturreview // literature review; Peergewalt // peer violence; Policies // policies; Prävalenz // prevalence; Prävention // prevention; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Sicherheit // safety; Sport // sports

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 2.2.3.1.1 Sportunterricht; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

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Schlagwörter:

Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; kognitive Beeinträchtigung // intellectual disabilities; Literaturreview // literature review; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

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Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Gesundheit // health; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Prävalenz // prevalence; Prävention // prevention; Schwarz // Black; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; international // international; kognitive Beeinträchtigung // intellectual disabilities; Literaturreview // literature review; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.4 Sonderpädagogik; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Ethnizität // ethnicity; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität

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LGBTQI parented families and schools. Visibility, representation, and pride.

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Familie // family; Großbritannien // Great Britain; queer // queer; Schule // school

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Carter, Rona; Halawah, Amira; Trinh, Sarah L. (2018):

Peer Exclusion During the Pubertal Transition. The Role of Social Competence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (1), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0682-8.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Jugend // youth; Jungen // boys; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Peergruppe // peer group; Pubertät // Puberty; soziale Kompetenz // social competence; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 81, S. 214–224. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.05.004.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Sri Lanka // Sri Lanka; Survey // survey; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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In: *Journal of Adolescence* 69, S. 180–188. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.10.007.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Heirat // marriage; international // international; Jugend // youth; Literaturreview // literature review; Risiko // risk; Schule // school; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Citak Tunc, Gulseren; Gorak, Gulay; Ozyazicioglu, Nurcan; Ak, Bedriye; Isil, Ozlem; Vural, Pinar (2018):

Preventing Child Sexual Abuse. Body Safety Training for Young Children in Turkey.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (4), S. 347–364. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1477001.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Kinder // children; Kindertagesstätte // nursery; Körper // body; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Prävention // prevention; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Sicherheit // safety; Türkei // Turkey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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"What Will My Friends Think?". Social Consequences for Danish Victims of Sexual Assaults in Peer Groups.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (3), S. 217–236. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1425942.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Dänemark // Denmark; Europa // Europe; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Mixed methods // mixed methods; Peergewalt // peer violence; Peergruppe // peer group; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Sexual Self-Efficacy and Gender: A Review of Condom Use and Sexual Negotiation Among Young Men and Women in Sub-Saharan Africa.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (4-5), S. 522–539. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1421607.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Intervention // intervention; Jugend // youth; Literaturreview // literature review; Prävention // prevention; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (3), S. 534–546. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0734-0.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Corbett, Annie (2018):

The voices of survivors. An exploration of the contributing factors that assisted with exiting from commercial sexual exploitation in childhood.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 85, S. 91–98. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.12.009.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Menschenhandel // human trafficking; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Cordisco Tsai, Laura (2018):

Conducting Research with Survivors of Sex Trafficking. Lessons from a Financial Diaries Study in the Philippines.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 48 (1), S. 158–175. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcx017.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Menschenhandel // human trafficking; Methodologie // methodology; Philippinen // Philippines; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Cumming-Potvin, Wendy; Martino, Wayne (2018):

The policyscape of transgender equality and gender diversity in the Western Australian education system. A case study.

In: *Gender and Education* 30 (6), S. 715–735. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2018.1483491.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Policies // policies; Politik // politics; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schule // school; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Cumming-Potvin, Wendy M.; Martino, Wayne (2018):

Countering heteronormativity and cisnormativity in Australian schools. Examining English teachers' reflections on gender and sexual diversity in the classroom.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 74, S. 35–48. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2018.04.008.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Cisnormativität // cisnormativity; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Lehrer*innen // teachers; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; queer // queer; Schule // school; Sprache // language; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

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Dutch Adolescents' Everyday Expressions of Sexual Behavior Trajectories Over a 2-Year Period. A Mixed-Methods Study.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (6), S. 1811–1823. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1224-5.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Methodologie // methodology; Mixed methods // mixed methods; Niederlande // Netherlands; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Davis, Angela C.; Carrotte, Elise R.; Hellard, Margaret E.; Lim, Megan S. C. (2018):

What Behaviors Do Young Heterosexual Australians See in Pornography? A Cross-Sectional Study.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (3), S. 310–319. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1417350.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Pornografie // pornography; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

DeLay, Dawn; Lynn Martin, Carol; Cook, Rachel E.; Hanish, Laura D. (2018):

The Influence of Peers During Adolescence: Does Homophobic Name Calling by Peers Change Gender Identity?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (3), S. 636–649. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0749-6.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; Theorie // theory; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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Lesbian, gay, and bisexual (LGB) youth within in welfare: Prevalence, risk and outcomes.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 80, S. 183–193. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.03.009.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Dodd, S. J.; Ruffins, Jeannette; Arzola, Denise (2018):

Improving Health While Saving Money. Lessons Learned from a Supportive Housing Program for Young Adults with HIV.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 163–171. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0287-8.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Gesundheit // health; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; obdachlos // homeless; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Ernberg, Emelie; Magnusson, Mikaela; Landström, Sara (2018):

Prosecution of Child Sexual Abuse Cases Involving Preschool-Aged Children: A Study of Swedish Cases from 2010 to 2014.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (7), S. 832–851. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1501786.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Kinder // children; Kindertagesstätte // nursery; Schweden // Sweden; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Ey, Lesley-anne; McInnes, Elspeth (2018):

Educators' Observations of Children's Display of Problematic Sexual Behaviors in Educational Settings.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (1), S. 88–105. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1349855.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Intervention // intervention; Kinder // children; Kinderbetreuung // child care; Kindertagesstätte // nursery; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Kirche // church; Pädagogische Fachkräfte // pedagogical staff; Prävention // prevention; Schule // school; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Fasula, Amy M.; Gray, Simone C.; Vereen, Rhyann N.; Carry, Monique; Sales, Jessica M.; Abad, Neetu et al. (2018):

Multiple psychosocial health problems and sexual risk among African American females in juvenile detention. A cross-sectional study.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 88, S. 74–80. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2018.02.041.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; Haft // detention; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schwarz // Black; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Fefferman, Ann M.; Upadhyay, Ushma D. (2018):

Hybrid Masculinity and Young Men's Circumscribed Engagement in Contraceptive Management.

In: *Gender & Society* 32 (3), S. 371–394. DOI: 10.1177/0891243218763313.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Jungen // boys; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Schwarz // Black; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Soziale Schicht // social class; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality; USA // USA; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Feinstein, Brian A.; Dellucci, Trey V.; Graham, Simon; Parsons, Jeffrey T.; Mustanski, Brian (2018):

Sexually transmitted infections among young men who have sex with men. Experiences with diagnosis, treatment, and reinfection.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 172–182. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0312-y.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Gesundheit // health; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Prävention // prevention; queer // queer; schwul // gay; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Firmin, Carlene (2018):

Contextual Risk, Individualised Responses. An Assessment of Safeguarding Responses to Nine Cases of Peer-on-Peer Abuse.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 27 (1), S. 42–57. DOI: 10.1002/car.2449.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Peergewalt // peer violence; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sicherheit // safety; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Fredlund, Cecilia; Dahlström, Örjan; Svedin, Carl Göran; Wadsby, Marie; Jonsson, Linda S.; Priebe, Gisela (2018):

Adolescents' motives for selling sex in a welfare state - A Swedish national study.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 81, S. 286–295. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.04.030.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Prostitution // prostitution; Schweden // Sweden; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Freitas, Donna (2018):

A culture of consent. How to fight sexual assault on campus.

New York: Oxford University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Rape Culture // rape culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Gámez-Guadix, Manuel; Almendros, Carmen; Calvete, Esther; Santisteban, Patricia de (2018):

Persuasion strategies and sexual solicitations and interactions in online sexual grooming of adolescents. Modeling direct and indirect pathways.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 63, S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.12.002.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Grooming // grooming; Internet // Internet; Intervention // intervention; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Medien // media; Prävention // prevention; Sexuelle Ausbeutung // sexual exploitation; Soziale Medien // social media; Spanien // Spain; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Garthe, Rachel C.; Sullivan, Terri N.; Farrell, Albert (2018):

Dating violence perpetration and perceived parental support for fighting and nonviolent responses to conflict. An autoregressive cross-lagged model.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 68, S. 221–231. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.08.006.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schwarz // Black; Soziale Schicht // social class; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Gerritse, Karl; Hartman, Laura; Antonides, Marte Fleur; Wensing-Kruger, Annelijn; Vries, Annelou L. C. de; Molewijk, Bert C. (2018):

Moral Challenges in Transgender Care. A Thematic Analysis Based on a Focused Ethnography.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (8), S. 2319–2333. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1287-3.

Schlagwörter:

Ethik // ethics; Ethnographie // ethnography; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Gesundheit // health; Klinik // clinic; Niederlande // Netherlands; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; queer // queer; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige;
3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern

Gervais, Christine L. M.; Romano, Elisa (2018):

Safeguarding child rights and enhancing caregiver responsibilities among Canadian parents of youth who sexually offend.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 76, S. 502–514. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.12.005.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Kanada // Canada; Nordamerika // North America; Peergewalt // peer violence; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen;
5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Gewirtz-Meydan, Ateret; Walsh, Wendy; Wolak, Janis; Finkelhor, David (2018):

The complex experience of child pornography survivors.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 80, S. 238–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.03.031.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Missbrauchsdarstellungen // child pornography; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch;
6.3 Negative Folgen

Gibbs, Deborah A.; Henninger, Alana M.; Tueller, Stephen J.; Kluckman, Marianne N. (2018):

Human trafficking and the child welfare population in Florida.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 88, S. 1–10. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2018.02.045.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Menschenhandel // human trafficking; Nordamerika // North America; Statistiken // statistics; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Goncy, Elizabeth A.; Farrell, Albert D.; Sullivan, Terri N. (2018):

Patterns of Change in Adolescent Dating Victimization and Aggression During Middle School.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (3), S. 501–514. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0715-3.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Nordamerika // North America; Schüler*innen // pupils; Soziale Schicht // social class; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Exploring Gender and Racial/Ethnic Differences in the Effects of Child Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (5), S. 570–587. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1484403.

Schlagwörter:

Bewältigung // coping; Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Intervention // intervention; Jugend // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Selbstmord // suicide; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Grest, Carolina Villamil; Amaro, Hortensia; Unger, Jennifer (2018):

Longitudinal Predictors of Intimate Partner Violence Perpetration and Victimization in Latino Emerging Adults.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (3), S. 560–574. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0663-y.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Latin@s // Latinx; Nordamerika // North America; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Grest, Carolina Villamil; Lee, Jungeun Olivia; Gilreath, Tamika; Unger, Jennifer B. (2018):

Latent Class Analysis of Intimate Partner Violence Perpetration and Victimization among Latino Emerging Adults.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (3), S. 575–585. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0807-0.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Latin@s // Latinx; Nordamerika // North America; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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The Roles of Self-Socialization and Parent Socialization in Toddlers' Gender-Typed Appearance.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (8), S. 2277–2285. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1263-y.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Kinder // children; Mutter // mother; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sozialisation // socialization; Stereotype // stereotypes; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Hall, Kelli Stidham; Manu, Abubakar; Morhe, Emmanuel; Harris, Lisa H.; Loll, Dana; Ela, Elizabeth et al. (2018):
Development and Validation of a Scale to Measure Adolescent Sexual and Reproductive Health Stigma. Results From Young Women in Ghana.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (1), S. 60–72. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1292493.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Ghana // Ghana; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Mädchen // girls; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Stigmatisierung // stigma; Survey // survey; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Harper, Craig A.; Perkins, Colin (2018):

Reporting Child Sexual Abuse within Religious Settings. Challenges and Future Directions.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 27 (1), S. 30–41. DOI: 10.1002/car.2484.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; international // international; Kinder // children; Religion // religion; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.5 Disclosure

Hart, Trevor A.; Noor, Syed W.; Vernon, Julia R. G.; Kidwai, Ammaar; Roberts, Karen; Myers, Ted; Calzavara, Liviana (2018):

Childhood Maltreatment, Bullying Victimization, and Psychological Distress Among Gay and Bisexual Men.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (4-5), S. 604–616. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1401972.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Homosexualität // homosexuality; Kanada // Canada; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Herriot, Lindsay; Burns, David P.; Yeung, Betty (2018):

Contested spaces. Trans-inclusive school policies and parental sovereignty in Canada.

In: *Gender and Education* 30 (6), S. 695–714. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2017.1396291.

Schlagwörter:

Aktivismus // activism; Eltern // parents; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kanada // Canada; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Politik // politics; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schule // school; Sicherheit // safety; Toiletten // bathroom; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Iyer, Padmini (2018):

From rakhi to romance. Negotiating 'acceptable' relationships in co-educational secondary schools in New Delhi, India.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 20 (3), S. 306–320. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2017.1346200.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Indien // India; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Mixed methods // mixed methods; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Jackson, Sue (2018):

Young feminists, feminism and digital media.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 28 (1), S. 32–49. DOI: 10.1177/0959353517716952.

Schlagwörter:

Aktivismus // activism; Feminismus // feminism; Geschlecht // gender; Medien // media; Sicherheit // safety; Soziale Medien // social media

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Jones, Lisa M.; Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Turner, Heather A.; Ybarra, Michele L. (2018):

Characteristics of bias-based harassment incidents reported by a national sample of U.S. adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 65, S. 50–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.02.013.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Peergewalt // peer violence; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Religion // religion; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Kahn, Nicole F.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2018):

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In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (6), S. 1791–1810. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1176-9.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Katz-Wise, Sabra L.; Ehrensaft, Diane; Veters, Ralph; Forcier, Michelle; Austin, S. Bryn (2018):

Family Functioning and Mental Health of Transgender and Gender-Nonconforming Youth in the Trans Teen and Family Narratives Project.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (4-5), S. 582–590. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1415291.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Geschwister // siblings; Jugend // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Survey // survey; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Kim, Youn Kyoung; Yang, Mi-Youn; Barthelemy, Juan J.; Lofaso, Blaine M. (2018):

A binary gender analysis to bullying, dating violence, and attempted suicide. The disproportionate effect of depression and psychological harm.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 90, S. 141–148. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2018.05.028.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt // violence; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; Peergewalt // peer violence; Schule // school; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Koçtürk, Nilüfer; Yüksel, Fadime (2018):

The Characteristics of Child Sexual Abuse in the School Environment in Turkey.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (7), S. 852–869. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1501787.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Europa // Europe; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Pädagogische Fachkräfte // pedagogical staff; Peergewalt // peer violence; Prävalenz // prevalence; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender; Türkei // Turkey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Kolenz, Kristen A.; Branfman, Jonathan (2018):

Laughing to sexual education. Feminist pedagogy of laughter as a model for holistic sex-education.

In: *Sex Education* 23 (4), S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2018.1559728.

Schlagwörter:

Feminismus // feminism; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Humor // humour; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Nordamerika // North America; Rassismus // racism; Sexismus // sexism; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Theorie // theory; Universität // college; USA // USA; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

Kugbey, Nuworza; Ayanore, Martin Amogre; Amu, Hubert; Oppong Asante, Kwaku; Adam, Awolu (2018):

International note. Analysis of risk and protective factors for risky sexual behaviours among school-aged adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 68, S. 66–69. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.06.013.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Ghana // Ghana; Intervention // intervention; Jugend // youth; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Kuperberg, Arielle; Walker, Alicia M. (2018):

Heterosexual College Students Who Hookup with Same-Sex Partners.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (5), S. 1387–1403. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1194-7.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Homosexualität // homosexuality; Identität // identity; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Labra, Oscar; Chamblas, Isis; Turcotte, Pierre; Dubé, Nico (2018):

Is It a Man's World? An Exploratory Study of Male Students in Social Work: Experiences from Chile.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 48 (3), S. 769–786. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcx065.

Schlagwörter:

Chile // Chile; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Männer // men; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Universität // college

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

Leander, Else-Marie Buch; Larsen, Per Lindsø; Munk, Karen Pallesgaard (2018):

Children's Doctor Games and Nudity at Danish Childcare Institutions.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (4), S. 863–875. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-017-1144-9.

Schlagwörter:

Dänemark // Denmark; Diskurs // discourse; Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Kinderbetreuung // child care; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Körper // body; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Internet // Internet; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Kommentar // commentary; Medien // media; Sexting // sexting; Soziale Medien // social media; Technologie // technology; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Kinder // children; ländlich // rural; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Religion // religion; Schulklima // school climate; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Stadt // urban; Tansania // Tanzania

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; USA // USA; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Administration // administration; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Politik // politics; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Demenz // dementia; Sexualität // sexuality; Wohlbefinden // well-being

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität

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In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (2), S. 321–333. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0733-1.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schutz // protection; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Internet // Internet; Jugend // youth; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Medien // media; Mentale

Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; Schüler*innen // pupils; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Mexiko // Mexico; Nordamerika // North America; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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The role of social media in sex education. Dispatches from queer, trans, and racialized communities.

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Schlagwörter:

Internet // Internet; Intersektionalität // intersectionality; Kommentar // commentary; Medien // media; queer // queer; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Soziale Medien // social media; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

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Beyond "Just Saying No". A Preliminary Evaluation of Strategies College Students Use to Refuse Sexual Activity.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (2), S. 341–351. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-017-1130-2.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kommunikation // communication; Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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Cambridge: MIT Press (MIT Press Ser).

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Homosexualität // homosexuality; international // international

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT

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In: *Journal of Adolescence* 69, S. 80–87. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.09.006.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Jungen // boys; Kroatien // Croatia; Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Pornografie // pornography; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Religion // religion; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Südafrika // South Africa

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Schlagwörter:

Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Heirat // marriage; Homosexualität // homosexuality; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT

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Young bisexual women's experiences in secondary schools.

New York, London: Routledge (Routledge critical studies in gender and sexuality in education, 10).

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Bisexualität // bisexuality; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Mädchen // girls; Neuseeland // New Zealand; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; queer // queer; Schule // school

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

McPhail, Ian V. (2018):

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In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (5), S. 1313–1317. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1198-3.

Schlagwörter:

Literaturreview // literature review; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Täter*in // offender; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

McPhail, Ian V.; Nunes, Kevin L.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Sewell, Rikki; Peacock, Edward J.; Looman, Jan; Fernandez, Yolanda M. (2018):

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In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (8), S. 2241–2254. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1288-2.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene // adults; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gefühle // emotions; Kanada // Canada; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (3), S. 601–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0783-4.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Freunde // friends; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jugend // youth; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; Peergewalt // peer violence; Peergruppe // peer group; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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In: *Sex Education* 18 (4), S. 449–463. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1411254.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Grundschule // elementary school; Kanada // Canada; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; queer // queer; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche

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Lanham: Lexington Books.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Rape Culture // rape culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

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Mechanisms Linking Self-Regulation and Sexual Behaviors in Never-Married Young Adults.

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Morrison, Sarah Elizabeth; Bruce, Caroline; Wilson, Sarah (2018):

Children's Disclosure of Sexual Abuse. A Systematic Review of Qualitative Research Exploring Barriers and Facilitators.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (2), S. 176–194. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1425943.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Evaluation // evaluation; Folgen // long-term effects; Literaturreview // literature review; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.5 Disclosure

Moynihan, Melissa; Mitchell, Katherine; Pitcher, Claire; Havaei, Farinaz; Ferguson, Max; Saewyc, Elizabeth (2018):

A systematic review of the state of the literature on sexually exploited boys internationally.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 76, S. 440–451. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.12.003.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungslücken; international // international; Jugend // youth; Jungen // boys; Kinder // children; Literaturreview // literature review; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Nappa, Maria Rosaria; Palladino, Benedetta Emanuela; Menesini, Ersilia; Baiocco, Roberto (2018):

Teachers' Reaction in Homophobic Bullying Incidents. The Role of Self-efficacy and Homophobic Attitudes.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 208–218. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0306-9.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Italien // Italy; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Mobbing // bullying; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schutz // protection

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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"I Have No Idea What's Going On Out There". Parents' Perspectives on Promoting Sexual Health in Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Adolescents.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 111–122. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-018-0326-0.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Kommunikation // communication; Nordamerika // North America; Peergruppe // peer group; queer // queer; schwul // gay; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

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Social Work Practice with Survivors of Sex Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation.

New York: Columbia University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Handbuch // handbook; Menschenhandel // human trafficking; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Sexuelle Ausbeutung // sexual exploitation; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Trauma // trauma

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (1), S. 84–98. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1342757.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gefühle // emotions; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Sport // sports; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

O'Brien, Jennifer E. (2018):

"Sometimes, Somebody Just Needs Somebody - Anybody - to Care". The power of interpersonal relationships in the lives of domestic minor sex trafficking survivors.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 81, S. 1–11. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.04.010.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Nordamerika // North America; pädagogische Beziehungsgestaltung // pedagogical relationship; Professionalität // professionalism; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Resilienz // resilience; Schutz // protection; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.4 Resilienz

O'Donohue, William; Cummings, Caroline; Willis, Brendan (2018):

The Frequency of False Allegations of Child Sexual Abuse. A Critical Review.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (5), S. 459–475. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1477224.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Literaturreview // literature review; Nordamerika // North America; Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Pariera, Katrina L.; Brody, Evan (2018):

"Talk More About It". Emerging Adults' Attitudes About How and When Parents Should Talk About Sex.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 219–229. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0314-9.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kommunikation // communication; Mixed methods // mixed methods; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche

Pingel, Emily S.; Bauermeister, José A. (2018):

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In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 20 (2), S. 218–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2017.1338756.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gemeinde // community; Gesundheit // health; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kirche // church; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Religion // religion; Schwarz // Black; schwul // gay; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Popović, Stjepka (2018):

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (7), S. 752–777. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1486935.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; international // international;
Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Literaturreview // literature review; Medien // media; Medienanalyse // media
analysis

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Preble, Kathleen M.; Black, Beverly M.; Weisz, Arlene N. (2018):

Teens' and parents' perceived levels of helpfulness. An examination of suggested "things to say" to youth experiencing Teen Dating Violence.

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Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Gewalt in
Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Menschenrechte // human rights; Nordamerika // North
America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; soziale Unterstützung // social support; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie;
6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Prino, Laura Elvira; Longobardi, Claudio; Settanni, Michele (2018):

Young Adult Retrospective Reports of Adverse Childhood Experiences: Prevalence of Physical, Emotional, and Sexual Abuse in Italy.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (6), S. 1769–1778. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-018-1154-2.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender;
Italien // Italy; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Prävalenz // prevalence; Survey
// survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Riggs, Damien W.; Bartholomaeus, Clare (2018):

Transgender young people's narratives of intimacy and sexual health. Implications for sexuality education.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (4), S. 376–390. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1355299.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; international // international; Intimität // intimacy; Schule // school;
Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit //
sexual health; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen;
2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Roberts, Louise; Long, Sara Jayne; Young, Honor; Hewitt, Gillian; Murphy, Simon; Moore, Graham F. (2018):

Sexual health outcomes for young people in state care. Cross-sectional analysis of a national survey and views of social care professionals in Wales.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 89, S. 281–288. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2018.04.044.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder- und
Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Pflegefamilie // foster care; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews;
Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Statistiken // statistics

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik;
4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Rosmarin, David H.; Pirutinsky, Steven; Appel, Moses; Kaplan, Talia; Pelcovitz, David (2018):

Childhood sexual abuse, mental health, and religion across the Jewish community.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 81, S. 21–28. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.04.011.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; Religion // religion; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Rúðólfssdóttir, Annadís G.; Jóhannsdóttir, Ásta (2018):

Fuck patriarchy! An analysis of digital mainstream media discussion of the #freethenipple activities in Iceland in March 2015.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 28 (1), S. 133–151. DOI: 10.1177/0959353517715876.

Schlagwörter:

Aktivismus // activism; Diskurs // discourse; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Europa // Europe; Feminismus // feminism; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Internet // Internet; Island // Iceland; Körper // body; Medien // media; Politik // politics; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Soziale Medien // social media

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Sanhueza, Tatiana; Lessard, Geneviève (2018):

Representations of dating violence in Chilean adolescents. A qualitative study.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 87, S. 41–51. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2018.02.004.

Schlagwörter:

Chile // Chile; Einstellungen // attitudes; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Lateinamerika // Latin America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schüler*innen // pupils

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Sanjakdar, Fida; Yip, Andrew Kam-Tuck (Hg.) (2018):

Critical Pedagogy, Sexuality Education and Young People. Issues about Democracy and Active Citizenry.

New York: Peter Lang (Adolescent Cultures, School, and Society, v.71).

Schlagwörter:

Jugend // youth; Pädagogik // pedagogy; Sexualerziehung // sex ed

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Sanjeevi, Jerusha; Houlihan, Daniel; Bergstrom, Kelly A.; Langley, Moses M.; Judkins, Jaxson (2018):

A Review of Child Sexual Abuse: Impact, Risk, and Resilience in the Context of Culture.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (6), S. 622–641. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1486934.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Resilienz // resilience;

Risiko // risk; Schutz // protection; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Sozialisation // socialization; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

Sauntson, Helen (2018):

Language, sexuality and education.

Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Nordamerika // North America; Pädagogik // pedagogy; queer // queer; Schule // school; Sprache // language; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Savasuk-Luxton, Rachel; Adler-Baeder, Francesca; Haselschwerdt, Megan L. (2018):

Understanding change in violence-related attitudes for adolescents in relationship education.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 63, S. 153–164. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.12.012.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Sawriker, Pooja; Katz, Ilan (2018):

Preventing child sexual abuse (CSA) in ethnic minority communities. A literature review and suggestions for practice in Australia.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 85, S. 174–186. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.12.028.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; international // international; Literaturreview // literature review; Migration // migration; Prävention // prevention; Schule // school; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Sawyer, Ashlee N.; Smith, Erin R.; Benotsch, Eric G. (2018):

Dating Application Use and Sexual Risk Behavior Among Young Adults.

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Internet // Internet; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Scott, Joan Wallach (2018):

Sex and secularism.

Princeton: Princeton University Press (The public square book series).

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Feminismus // feminism; Geschichte // history; Rassismus // racism; Sexismus // sexism

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität

Serrano, Jessica; Crouch, Julia M.; Albertson, Katie; Ahrens, Kym R. (2018):

Stakeholder perceptions of barriers and facilitators to sexual health discussions between foster and kinship caregivers and youth in foster care. A qualitative study.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 88, S. 434–440. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2018.03.020.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Nordamerika // North America; Pflegefamilie // foster care; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Shawler, Paul M.; Elizabeth Bard, M.; Taylor, Erin K.; Wilsie, Carisa; Funderburk, Beverly; Silovsky, Jane F. (2018):

Parent-Child Interaction Therapy and young children with Problematic Sexual Behavior. A conceptual overview and treatment considerations.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 84, S. 206–214. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.12.006.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Evaluation // evaluation; Kinder // children; Kindertagesstätte // nursery; Nordamerika // North America; Psychotherapie // psychotherapy; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Tabu // taboo; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Shelton, Stephanie Anne; Lester, Aryah O. S. (2018):

Finding possibilities in the impossible. A celebratory narrative of trans youth experiences in the Southeastern USA.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (4), S. 391–405. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1421920.

Schlagwörter:

Empowerment // empowerment; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Narration // narrative; Nordamerika // North America; Peergruppe // peer group; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Simons, Jack D.; Beck, Matthew J.; Asplund, Nancy R.; Chan, Christian D.; Byrd, Rebekah (2018):

Advocacy for gender minority students. Recommendations for school counsellors.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (4), S. 464–478. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1421531.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; queer // queer; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

Simpson, David M.; Leonhardt, Nathan D.; Hawkins, Alan J. (2018):

Learning About Love. A Meta-Analytic Study of Individually-Oriented Relationship Education Programs for Adolescents and Emerging Adults.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 47 (3), S. 477–489. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0725-1.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Literaturreview // literature review; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Sizemore, Kayla M.; Olmstead, Spencer B. (2018):

Willingness of Emerging Adults to Engage in Consensual Non-Monogamy. A Mixed-Methods Analysis.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (5), S. 1423–1438. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-017-1075-5.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Mixed methods // mixed methods; Nordamerika // North America; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Sklenarova, Halina; Schulz, Anja; Schuhmann, Petya; Osterheider, Michael; Neutze, Janina (2018):

Online sexual solicitation by adults and peers. Results from a population based German sample.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 76, S. 225–236. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.11.005.

Schlagwörter:

Deutschland // Germany; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Internet // Internet; Jugend // youth; Medien // media; Sexting // sexting; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Soler, Jorge H.; Caldwell, Cleopatra H.; Córdova, David; Harper, Gary; Bauermeister, José A. (2018):

Who Counts as Family? Family Typologies, Family Support, and Family Undermining Among Young Adult Gay and Bisexual Men.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 123–138. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0288-7.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; schwul // gay; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Steenbakkers, Anne; Ellingsen, Ingunn T.; van der Steen, Steffie; Grietens, Hans (2018):

Do Foster Parents and Care Workers Recognize the Needs of Youth in Family Foster Care with a History of Sexual Abuse?

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (7), S. 811–831. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2018.1520378.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Niederlande // Netherlands; pädagogische Beziehungsgestaltung // pedagogical relationship; Partizipation // participation; Pflegefamilie // foster care; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Stubbs-Richardson, Megan; Rader, Nicole E.; Cosby, Arthur G. (2018):

Tweeting rape culture. Examining portrayals of victim blaming in discussions of sexual assault cases on Twitter.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 28 (1), S. 90–108. DOI: 10.1177/0959353517715874.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Internet // Internet; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Rape Culture // rape culture; Soziale Medien // social media; USA // USA; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Stulberg, Lisa M. (2018):

LGBTQ Social Movements.

Newark: Polity Press (Social Movements Ser). Online verfügbar unter <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/gbv/detail.action?docID=5226123>.

Schlagwörter:

Aktivismus // activism; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; lesbisch // lesbian; queer // queer; schwul // gay; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Sun, Wai Han; Miu, Heidi Yin Hai; Wong, Carlos King Ho; Tucker, Joseph D.; Wong, William Chi Wai (2018):

Assessing Participation and Effectiveness of the Peer-Led Approach in Youth Sexual Health Education. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis in More Developed Countries.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (1), S. 31–44. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1247779.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; Peergruppe // peer group; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.3 Peers; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Thomas, Sara E. (2018):

“What Should I Do?”. Young Women’s Reported Dilemmas with Nude Photographs.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 15 (2), S. 192–207. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0310-0.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Geschlecht // gender; Internet // Internet; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; Sexting // sexting; Soziale Medien // social media; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Thorsen, Maggie L. (2018):

A Latent Class Analysis of Behavioral and Psychosocial Dimensions of Adolescent Sexuality: Exploring Race Differences.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (1), S. 45–59. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1254143.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Sozialisation // socialization; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Tomaszewska, Paulina; Krahé, Barbara (2018):

Predictors of Sexual Aggression Victimization and Perpetration Among Polish University Students: A Longitudinal Study.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 47 (2), S. 493–505. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0823-2.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Konsens // consent; Polen // Poland; Pornografie // pornography; Prävention // prevention; Religion // religion; Risiko // risk; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelle Skripte // sexual scripts; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Trekels, Jolien; Eggermont, Steven (2018):

"I Can/Should Look Like a Media Figure": The Association Between Direct and Indirect Media Exposure and Teens' Sexualizing Appearance Behaviors.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (3), S. 320–333. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1387754.

Schlagwörter:

Belgien // Belgium; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Körper // body; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Medien // media; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Ullman, Jacqueline; Ferfolja, Tania (Hg.) (2018):

Gender and sexuality in education and health. Advocating for equity and social justice.

London, New York: Routledge.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Geschlecht // gender; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

van Beveren, Laura; Rutten, Kris; Vandermeersche, Geert; Verdoodt, Ive (2018):

Exploring educational taboos through school movies. A rhetorical analysis of student-teachers' reflections.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 75, S. 187–198. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2018.06.008.

Schlagwörter:

Ausbildung // qualification; Belgien // Belgium; Ethnographie // ethnography; Europa // Europe; Film // movie; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Medien // media; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Wallis, Pete; Wallis, Thalia (2018):

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Schlagwörter:

Jugend // youth; Konsens // consent; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Peergewalt // peer violence; Peergruppe // peer group; Sexualerziehung // sex ed

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Wamser-Nanney, Rachel; Sager, Julia C. (2018):

Predictors of maternal support following children's sexual abuse disclosures.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 81, S. 39–47. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.04.016.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

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Examining the utility of a train-the-trainer model for dissemination of sexual violence prevention in schools.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 80, S. 70–79. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2018.03.022.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Willoughby, Brian J.; Young-Petersen, Bonnie; Leonhardt, Nathan D. (2018):

Exploring Trajectories of Pornography Use Through Adolescence and Emerging Adulthood.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 55 (3), S. 297–309. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1368977.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; Pornografie // pornography; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Wolfe, Melissa Joy (2018):

Materialising effects of difference in sex education. The 'absurd' banana penis.

In: *Gender and Education* 30 (8), S. 1065–1077. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2018.1451625.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Film // movie; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Mädchen // girls; Mixed methods // mixed methods; Pädagogik // pedagogy; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Survey // survey; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Worley, Karen B.; Church, Janice K.; Worthington, Toss; Swearingen, Christopher J.; Jones, Jerry G. (2018):

Parents' perceptions of the value of sexual abuse medical evaluations of their children.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 88, S. 486–489. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2018.04.005.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Wubs, Dorijn; Batstra, Laura; Grietens, Hans W. E. (2018):

Speaking With and Without Words. An Analysis of Foster Children's Expressions and Behaviors That Are Suggestive of Prior Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 27 (1), S. 70–87. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1390716.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Niederlande // Netherlands; Pflegefamilie // foster care

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Yates, Peter (2018):

'Siblings as Better Together'. Social Worker Decision Making in Cases Involving Sibling Sexual Behaviour.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 48 (1), S. 176–194. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcx018.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschwister // siblings; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Grounded Theory // Grounded Theory; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Peergewalt // peer violence; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

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In: *Journal of Adolescence* 64, S. 89–97. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.02.006.

Schlagwörter:

Bewältigung // coping; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt // violence; Intervention // intervention; Jugend // youth; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Yoon, Yoewon; Cederbaum, Julie A.; Schwartz, Alix (2018):

Childhood sexual abuse and current suicidal ideation among adolescents. Problem-focused and emotion-focused coping skills.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 67, S. 120–128. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.06.009.

Schlagwörter:

Bewältigung // coping; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Jugend // youth; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Selbstmord // suicide; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Yu, Bin; Chen, Xinguang; Stanton, Bonita; Chen, Ding-Geng Din; Xu, Yunan; Wang, Yan (2018):

Quantum changes in self-efficacy and condom-use intention among youth. A chained cusp catastrophe model.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 68, S. 187–197. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.07.020.

Schlagwörter:

Bahamas // Bahamas; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; Peergruppe // peer group; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Yu, Rongqin; Pepler, Debra J.; van de Bongardt, Daphne; Josephson, Wendy L.; Connolly, Jennifer (2018):

Internalizing symptoms and dating violence perpetration in adolescence.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 69, S. 88–91. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.09.008.

Schlagwörter:

Bewältigung // coping; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Kanada // Canada; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Zerubavel, Eviatar (2018):

Taken for granted. The remarkable power of the unremarkable.

Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Geschlecht // gender; Privilegien // privilege; queer // queer; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse

2. 2017

Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Maravilla, Joemer Calderon; Williams, Gail; Najman, Jake Moses (2017):
Gender differences in the association between childhood sexual abuse and risky sexual behaviours. A systematic review and meta-analysis.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 249–260. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.11.023.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Literaturreview // literature review; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Reviktimisierung // revictimization; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Abidin, Crystal (2017):

Sex Bait. Sex Talk on Commercial Blogs as Informal Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 493–508.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Internet // Internet; Medien // media; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Singapur // Singapore

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Adjei, Jones K.; Saewyc, Elizabeth M. (2017):

Boys are not exempt. Sexual exploitation of adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 65, S. 14–23. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.01.001.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; international // international; Jugend // youth; Jungen // boys; Policies // policies; Prävention // prevention; Prostitution // prostitution; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Ahern, Elizabeth C.; Sadler, Leslie H.; Lamb, Michael E.; Gariglietti, Gianna M. (2017):

Wellbeing of Professionals Working with Suspected Victims of Child Sexual Exploitation.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (2), S. 130–140. DOI: 10.1002/car.2439.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Bewältigung // coping; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 6.5 Disclosure

Alix, Stephanie; Cossette, Louise; Hebert, Martine; Cyr, Mireille; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2017):

Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Suicidal Ideation Among Sexually Abused Adolescent Girls. The Mediating Role of Shame.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 158–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280577.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Selbstmord // suicide; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey; Trauma // trauma; USA // USA

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Allred, Pam; Fox, Nick J. (2017):

Materialism and Micropolitics in Sexualities Education Research. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

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Schlagwörter:

Methodologie // methodology; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Allen, Louisa (2017):

The Power of Things! A 'New' Ontology of Sexuality at School. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 611–630.

Schlagwörter:

Methodologie // methodology; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Allen, Louisa; Quinlivan, Kathleen (2017):

A Radical Plurality. Re-thinking Cultural and Religious Diversity in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 177–189.

Schlagwörter:

Interkulturell // intercultural; Religion // religion; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Lou (Hg.) (2017):

The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan.

Schlagwörter:

Handbuch // handbook; international // international; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

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Lifetime prevalence and incidence of sexual victimization of adolescents in institutional care.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 66, S. 23–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.015.

Schlagwörter:

Deutschland // Germany; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heim // residential care; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Peergewalt // peer violence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Almog, Ran; Kaplan, Danny (2017):

The Nerd and His Discontent.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 20 (1), S. 27–48. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15613831.

Schlagwörter:

Empowerment // empowerment; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kommentar // commentary; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Arbeit, Miriam R. (2017):

"Make Sure You're Not Getting Yourself in Trouble". Building Sexual Relationships and Preventing Sexual Violence at the U.S. Military Academy at West Point.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (8), S. 949–961. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1207055.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Grounded Theory // Grounded Theory; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Aygor, Hamide; Altuntug, Kamile; Ege, Emel (2017):

The Views of Students on Sexual Health and Reproductive Health Course.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (3), S. 387–394. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9489-5.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Klinik // clinic; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Türkei // Turkey; Universität // college

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Baams, Laura; Dubas, Judith Semon; van Aken, Marcel A. G. (2017):

Comprehensive Sexuality Education as a Longitudinal Predictor of LGBTQ Name-Calling and Perceived Willingness to Intervene in School.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 931–942. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0638-z.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jugend // youth; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Mobbing // bullying; Niederlande // Netherlands; queer // queer; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Badenes-Ribera, Laura; Frias-Navarro, Dolores; Berrios-Riquelme, Jose; Longobardi, Claudio (2017):

Italian Validation of the Queer/Liberationist Scale (Short Version) in a Sample of University Students. Confirmatory Factor Analysis.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 157–170. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0256-7.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Homosexualität // homosexuality; Italien // Italy; Methodologie // methodology; Politik // politics; Religion // religion; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Universität // college; Vorurteile // prejudices

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Ballan, Michelle S.; Freyer, Molly Burke (2017):

Autism Spectrum Disorder, Adolescence, and Sexuality Education. Suggested Interventions for Mental Health Professionals.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (2), S. 261–273. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9477-9.

Schlagwörter:

Autismus // autism; Behinderung // disability; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Literaturreview // literature review; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Barcelos, Chris (2017):

Culture, Contraception, and Colorblindness. Youth Sexual Health Promotion as a Gendered Racial Project.

In: *Gender & Society* 32 (2), S. 252–273. DOI: 10.1177/0891243217745314.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnographie // ethnography; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Latin@s // Latinx; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Rassismus // racism; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; USA // USA; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Bartholomaeus, Clare; Riggs, Damien W.; Andrew, Yarrow (2017):

The capacity of South Australian primary school teachers and pre-service teachers to work with trans and gender diverse students.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 65, S. 127–135. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2017.03.006.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Coming out // coming out; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Haltung // attitude; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Professionalität // professionalism; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2017):

Critically Sex/Ed. Asking Critical Questions of Neoliberal Truths in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): *The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education*.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 343–367.

Schlagwörter:

Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Bennett, Clare; Harden, Jane; Anstey, Sally (2017):

Fathers as sexuality educators. Aspirations and realities. An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (1), S. 74–89. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1390449.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Bentrott, Merea D.; Margrett, Jennifer A. (2017):

Adopting a Multilevel Approach to Protecting Residents' Rights to Sexuality in the Long-Term Care Environment. Policies, Staff Training, and Response Strategies.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (4), S. 359–369. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0260-y.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Erwachsene // adults; Ethik // ethics; Literaturreview // literature review; Policies // policies; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Berry, Lauren Janine; Tully, Ruth J.; Egan, Vincent (2017):

A Case Study Approach to Reducing the Risks of Child Sexual Exploitation (CSE).

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (7), S. 769–784. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1360428.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder // children; Kinderbetreuung // child care; Mädchen // girls; Risiko // risk; Sexuelle Ausbeutung // sexual exploitation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Bianchi, Dora; Morelli, Mara; Baiocco, Roberto; Chirumbolo, Antonio (2017):

Sexting as the mirror on the wall. Body-esteem attribution, media models, and objectified-body consciousness.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 61, S. 164–172. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.10.006.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Internet // Internet; Italien // Italy; Jugend // youth; Körper // body; Medien // media; Peergewalt // peer violence; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexting // sexting; sexuelle Identität // sexual identity; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Björnsdóttir, Kristín; Stefánsdóttir, Ástríður; Stefánsdóttir, Guðrún Valgerður (2017):

People with Intellectual Disabilities Negotiate Autonomy, Gender and Sexuality.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (3), S. 295–311. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9492-x.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Ethnographie // ethnography; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Island // Iceland; Männlichkeit // masculinity; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualität // sexuality; Weiblichkeit // femininity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Bonache, Helena; Gonzalez-Mendez, Rosaura; Krahé, Barbara (2017):

Romantic Attachment, Conflict Resolution Styles, and Teen Dating Violence Victimization.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (9), S. 1905–1917. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0635-2.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Spanien // Spain; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Borawska-Charko, Magdalena; Rohleder, Poul; Finlay, W. Mick. L. (2017):

The Sexual Health Knowledge of People with Intellectual Disabilities. A Review.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (4), S. 393–409. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0267-4.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; kognitive Beeinträchtigung // intellectual disabilities; Literaturreview // literature review; Narration // narrative; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Botfield, Jessica R.; Newman, Christy E.; Zwi, Anthony B. (2017):

Drawing them in. Professional perspectives on the complexities of engaging 'culturally diverse' young people with sexual and reproductive health promotion and care in Sydney, Australia.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (4), S. 438–452. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1233354.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geflohene // refugees; junge Erwachsene // young adults; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Boustani, Maya M.; Frazier, Stacy L.; Lesperance, Nephtalie (2017):

Sexual health programming for vulnerable youth. Improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 375–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.01.013.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Heim // residential care; Jugend // youth; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht // social class; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Brennan, Margaret; Hammond, Sean (2017):

A methodology for profiling paraphilic interest in Child Sexual Exploitation Material users on peer-to-peer networks.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 90–103. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241308.

Schlagwörter:

Methodologie // methodology; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Sexuelle Ausbeutung // sexual exploitation; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Brickman, Jared; Willoughby, Jessica Fitts (2017):

'You shouldn't be making people feel bad about having sex'. Exploring young adults' perceptions of a sex-positive sexual health text message intervention.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (6), S. 621–634. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1332582.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Brömdal, Annette; Rasmussen, Mary Lou; Sanjakdar, Fida; Allen, Louisa; Quinlivan, Kathleen (2017):

Intersex Bodies in Sexuality Education. On the Edge of Cultural Difference. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 369–390.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Intergeschlechtlichkeit // intersex; Neuseeland // New Zealand; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Brown, Juliana; Schmidt, Johanna; Robertson, Neville (2017):

“We’re like the sex CPR dummies”. Young women’s understandings of (hetero)sexual pleasure in university accommodation.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 28 (2), S. 253–271. DOI: 10.1177/0959353517742500.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Neuseeland // New Zealand; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexismus // sexism; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Universität // college; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Brownlie, E. B.; Graham, Eva; Bao, Lin; Koyama, Emiko; Beitchman, Joseph H. (2017):

Language disorder and retrospectively reported sexual abuse of girls. Severity and disclosure.

In: *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 58 (10), S. 1114–1121. DOI: 10.1111/jcpp.12723.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kanada // Canada; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Mädchen // girls; Methodologie // methodology; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Sprache // language; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Buck, Gillian; Lawrence, Angela; Ragonese, Ester (2017):

Exploring Peer Mentoring as a Form of Innovative Practice with Young People at Risk of Child Sexual Exploitation.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 47 (6), S. 1745–1763. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcx089.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Peergruppe // peer group; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.3 Peers; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Burgess-Proctor, Amanda; Comartin, Erin B.; Kubiak, Sheryl P. (2017):

Comparing Female- and Male-Perpetrated Child Sexual Abuse. A Mixed-Methods Analysis.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (6), S. 657–676. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1336504.

Schlagwörter:

Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Mixed methods // mixed methods; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Burns, Melanie C. (2017):

Mixed messages. Inconsistent sexual scripts in Australian teenage magazines and implications for sexual health practices.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (2), S. 191–205. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1415876.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Skripte // sexual scripts; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Byron, Paul (2017):

Friendship, sexual intimacy and young people's negotiations of sexual health.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (4), S. 486–500. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1239133.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Freunde // friends; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.3 Peers; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Byron, Paul; Hunt, Jessie (2017):

'That happened to me too'. Young people's informal knowledge of diverse genders and sexualities.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (3), S. 319–332. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1292899.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Jugend // youth; Peergruppe // peer group; queer // queer; Schule // school; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 4.3 Peers; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Canan, Sasha N.; Jozkowski, Kristen N. (2017):

Sexual Health Education Topics in Schools. Inclusion and Timing Preferences of a Sample of Southern U.S. College Students.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 143–156. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0251-z.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Carboni, Nicci; Bhana, Deevia (2017):

Forbidden fruit. The politics of researching young people's use of online sexually explicit materials in South African schools.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (6), S. 635–646. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1344629.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungsethik // research ethics; Internet // Internet; Medien // media; Methodologie // methodology; Policies // policies; Pornografie // pornography; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Südafrika // South Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Casey, Erin A.; Tolman, Richard M.; Carlson, Juliana; Allen, Christopher T.; Storer, Heather L. (2017):

What Motivates Men's Involvement in Gender-based Violence Prevention? Latent Class Profiles and Correlates in an International Sample of Men.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 20 (3), S. 294–316. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X16634801.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt // violence; Männer // men; Prävention // prevention; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Chappell, Paul (2017):

Dangerous girls and cheating boys. Zulu-speaking disabled young peoples' constructs of heterosexual relationships in Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (5), S. 587–600. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1256433.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Behinderung // disability; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Südafrika // South Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Choi, Hye Jeong; Weston, Rebecca; Temple, Jeff R. (2017):

A Three-Step Latent Class Analysis to Identify How Different Patterns of Teen Dating Violence and Psychosocial Factors Influence Mental Health.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (4), S. 854–866. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0570-7.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Chouliara, Zoë; Narang, Javita (2017):

Recovery from child sexual abuse (CSA) in India. A relational framework for practice.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 79, S. 527–538. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2017.06.072.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Indien // India; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Chronaki, Despina (2017):

What Does the News Teach Young People About Sex? In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): *The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education*.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 423–437.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Medien // media; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Coburn, Patricia I.; Chong, Kristin; Connolly, Deborah A. (2017):

The Effect of Case Severity on Sentence Length in Cases of Child Sexual Assault in Canada.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 319–333. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1283651.

Schlagwörter:

Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Kanada // Canada; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.5 Disclosure

Cody, Claire (2017):

'We have personal experience to share, it makes it real'. Young people's views on their role in sexual violence prevention efforts.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 79, S. 221–227. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2017.06.015.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; international // international; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Peergruppe // peer group; Prävention // prevention; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.3 Peers; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Coffelt, Tina A. (2017):

Deciding to reveal sexual information and sexuality education in mother-daughter relationships.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (5), S. 571–587. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1326377.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Coll, Leanne; O'Sullivan, Mary; Enright, Eimear (2017):

'The Trouble with Normal'. (re)imagining sexuality education with young people.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (2), S. 157–171. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1410699.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; Partizipation // participation; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Garrido, Edward F. (2017):

Current issues in child sexual abuse, gender and health outcomes: Shedding new lights to inform worldwide policy and practice.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 245–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.11.032.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Literaturreview // literature review; Policies // policies; Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Coolhart, Deborah; Brown, Maria T. (2017):

The need for safe spaces. Exploring the experiences of homeless LGBTQ youth in shelters.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 82, S. 230–238. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2017.09.021.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Grounded Theory // Grounded Theory; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Nordamerika // North America; obdachlos // homeless; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; queer // queer; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Correa, Ana Belén; Castro, Ángel; Barrada, Juan Ramón; Ruiz-Gómez, Paula (2017):

Sociodemographic and Psychosexual Characteristics of Students from a Spanish University Who Engage in Casual Sex.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (4), S. 445–453. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0274-0.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Spanien // Spain; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Universität // college; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Craig, Amber N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Janssen, Erick; Goodrich, David; Heiman, Julia R. (2017):

Affect and Sexual Responsivity in Men With and Without a History of Sexual Aggression.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (8), S. 984–993. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1301357.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression // aggression; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Crandall, AliceAnn; Magnusson, Brianna M.; Novilla, M. Lelinneth B.; Novilla, Lynneth Kirsten B.; Dyer, W. Justin (2017):

Family Financial Stress and Adolescent Sexual Risk-Taking: The Role of Self-Regulation.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 45–62. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0543-x.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gefühle // emotions; Jugend // youth; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht // social class; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Cree, Vivienne (2017):

'Khaki Fever' during the First World War. A Historical Case Study of Social Work's Approach towards Young Women, Sex and Moral Danger.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 1839–1854. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv103.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Frauen // women; Geschichte // history; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungslücken; Internet // Internet; Medien // media; Methodologie // methodology; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

DeLay, Dawn; Hanish, Laura D.; Zhang, Linlin; Martin, Carol Lynn (2017):

Assessing the Impact of Homophobic Name Calling on Early Adolescent Mental Health: A Longitudinal Social Network Analysis of Competing Peer Influence Effects.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 955–969. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0598-8.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jugend // youth; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Gruppensettings // group settings; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sexuelle Ausbeutung // sexual exploitation; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

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In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.

Schlagwörter:

Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Nordamerika // North America; Professionalität // professionalism; queer // queer; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Dessel, Adrienne B.; Rodenburg, Nancy (2017):

Social Workers and LGBT Policies. Attitude Predictors and Cultural Competence Course Outcomes.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (1), S. 17–31. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0231-3.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; queer // queer; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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Gang masculinity and high-risk sexual behaviours.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (2), S. 165–178. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1213422.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gangs // gangs; Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt // violence; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Latin@s // Latinx; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Schwarz // Black; Sexualität // sexuality; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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The Impact of Culture on Attitudes Toward the Sexuality of People with Intellectual Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (2), S. 245–260. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9484-x.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; Stigmatisierung // stigma; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.5 Disclosure

Doty, Jennifer L.; Gower, Amy L.; Rudi, Jessie H.; McMorris, Barbara J.; Borowsky, Iris W. (2017):

Patterns of Bullying and Sexual Harassment: Connections with Parents and Teachers as Direct Protective Factors.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (11), S. 2289–2304. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0698-0.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Dyer, Hannah (2017):

Reparation for a violent boyhood. Pedagogies of mourning in Shane Meadow's This is England.

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 25 (3), S. 315–325. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2016.1255244.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Film // movie; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Jungen // boys; Kinder // children; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Medienanalyse // media analysis; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Trauma // trauma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Embregts, Petri J. C. M.; Heestermans, Marianne; van den Bogaard, Kim J. H. M. (2017):

A Training Course for Psychologists. Learning to Assess (Alleged) Sexual Abuse Among Victims and Perpetrators Who Have Intellectual Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 39–44. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9476-x.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Niederlande // Netherlands; Prävention // prevention; Psychotherapie // psychotherapy; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern

Emmerink, Peggy M. J.; van den Eijnden, Regina J. J. M.; ter Bogt, Tom F. M.; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2017):

A Scale for the Assessment of Sexual Standards Among Youth. Psychometric Properties.

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Jungen // boys; Mädchen // girls; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Methodologie // methodology; Niederlande // Netherlands; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Ericsson, Stina; Boyd, Sally (2017):

Children's ongoing and relational negotiation of informed assent in child–researcher, child–child and child–parent interaction.

In: *Childhood* 24 (3), S. 300–315. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216688246.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnographie // ethnography; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungsethik // research ethics; Kinder // children; Konsens // consent; Methodologie // methodology; Partizipation // participation; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schweden // Sweden

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Espinosa-Hernandez, Graciela; Vasilenko, Sara A.; McPherson, Jenna L.; Gutierrez, Estefania; Rodriguez, Andrea (2017):

Brief report. The role of three dimensions of sexual well-being in adolescents' life satisfaction.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 61–65. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.009.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Latin@s // Latinx; Sexualität // sexuality; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Ey, Lesley-anne; McInnes, Elspeth; Rigney, Lester Irabinna (2017):

Educators' understanding of young children's typical and problematic sexual behaviour and their training in this area.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (6), S. 682–696. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1357030.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinderbetreuung // child care; Kindertagesstätte // nursery; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Schule // school; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Falligant, John Michael; Alexander, Apryl A.; Burkhart, Barry. R. (2017):

Offence characteristics and cognitive functioning in juveniles adjudicated for illegal sexual behaviour.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (3), S. 291–299. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1362271.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Fanniff, Amanda M.; Schubert, Carol A.; Mulvey, Edward P.; Iselin, Anne-Marie R.; Piquero, Alex R. (2017):

Risk and Outcomes. Are Adolescents Charged with Sex Offenses Different from Other Adolescent Offenders?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (7), S. 1394–1423. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0536-9.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Ferguson, Christopher J.; Donnellan, M. Brent (2017):

Are Associations Between "Sexist" Video Games and Decreased Empathy Toward Women Robust? A Reanalysis of Gabbiadini et al. 2016.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (12), S. 2446–2459. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0700-x.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Mädchen // girls; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Medien // media; Methodologie // methodology; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexismus // sexism; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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Sexuality Education in the Context of Mass Incarceration. Interruptions and Entanglements. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 279–300.

Schlagwörter:

Haft // detention; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017):

Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Jugend // youth; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Flink, Ilse Johanna Elisabeth; Mbaye, Solange Marie Odile; Diouf, Simon Richard Baye; Baumgartner, Sophie; Okur, Pinar (2017):

Collaboration between a child telephone helpline and sexual and reproductive health and rights organisations in Senegal. Lessons learned.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (1), S. 32–46. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1376276.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Senegal // Senegal; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Foster, Jennifer M. (2017):

It Happened to Me. A Qualitative Analysis of Boys' Narratives About Child Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (7), S. 853–873. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1360426.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Jungen // boys; Kinder // children; Narration // narrative; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Francia, Guadalupe; Edling, Silvia (2017):

Children's rights and violence. A case analysis at a Swedish boarding school.

In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 51–67. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216634063.

Schlagwörter:

Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Internat // boarding school; Kinder // children; Kinderrechte // children's rights; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schweden // Sweden

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt

Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017):

Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.11.009.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Pädagogische Fachkräfte // pedagogical staff; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

French, Bryana H.; Suh, Han Na; Arterberry, Brooke (2017):

Exploratory Factor Analysis and Psychometric Properties of the Sexual Coercion Inventory.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (8), S. 962–970. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1235129.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Methodologie // methodology; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Survey // survey; Universität // college; USA // USA; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Frias-Navarro, Dolores; Badenes-Ribera, Laura; Monverde-i-Bort, Hector (2017):

Evidence of Validity of the Beliefs About Children's Adjustment in Same-Sex Families Scale.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 171–181. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0246-9.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Homosexualität // homosexuality; Kinder // children; Spanien // Spain; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Friesen, Norm (2017):

The pedagogical relation past and present. Experience, subjectivity and failure.

In: *Journal of Curriculum Studies* 49 (6), S. 743–756. DOI: 10.1080/00220272.2017.1320427.

Schlagwörter:

Lehrer*innen // teachers; Pädagogik // pedagogy; pädagogische Beziehungsgestaltung // pedagogical relationship; Professionalität // professionalism; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

Gerbild, H.; Larsen, C. M.; Rolander, B.; Areskoug Josefsson, K. (2017):

Health Care Students' Attitudes Towards Addressing Sexual Health in Their Future Professional Work. Psychometrics of the Danish version of the Students' Attitudes Towards Addressing Sexual Health Scale.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 73–87. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9469-1.

Schlagwörter:

Dänemark // Denmark; Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Methodologie // methodology; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Gesser-Edelsburg, Anat; Fridman, Talia; Lev-Wiesel, Rachel (2017):

Edutainment as a Strategy for Parental Discussion With Israeli Children. The Potential of a Children's Play in Preventing Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (5), S. 553–572. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1319003.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Intervention // intervention; Israel // Israel; Kinder // children; Medien // media; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Soziale Schicht // social class

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Gilbert, Jen (2017):

Contesting consent in sex education.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (3), S. 268–279. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1393407.

Schlagwörter:

Aktivismus // activism; Diskurs // discourse; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kanada // Canada; Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; Schule // school; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; queer // queer

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

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Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors.

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Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Schwarz // Black; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Soziale Schicht // social class; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality; Südafrika // South Africa; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Intervention // intervention; Irland // ireland; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Gray, Matt J.; Hassija, Christina M.; Steinmetz, Sarah E. (2017):

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Schlagwörter:

Policies // policies; Prävention // prevention; Rape Culture // rape culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Universität // college

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

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In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 72, S. 22–31. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.07.004.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Spanien // Spain; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.5 Disclosure

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (6), S. 731–751. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1332704.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Psychotherapie // psychotherapy; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Grundmann, Dorit; Krupp, Jurian; Scherner, Gerold; Amelung, Till; Beier, Klaus Michael (2017):

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Schlagwörter:

Deutschland // Germany; Europa // Europe; Kommentar // commentary; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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In: *Sex Education* 17 (5), S. 529–543. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1315933.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gruppensettings // group settings; Jugend // youth; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Risiko // risk; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Uganda // Uganda; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Slut-shaming and victim-blaming. A qualitative investigation of undergraduate students' perceptions of sexual violence.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (6), S. 697–711. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1362332.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Nordamerika // North America; Opferbeschuldigung // victim-blaming; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergreif

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Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Diskurs // discourse; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Mobbing // bullying; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; queer // queer; Schulklima // school climate; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; Soziale Arbeit // social work; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Hallett, Sophie (2017):

'An Uncomfortable Comfortableness'. 'Care', Child Protection and Child Sexual Exploitation.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 2137–2152. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv136.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Harper, Craig A.; Bartels, Ross M. (2017):

The influence of implicit theories and offender characteristics on judgements of sexual offenders. A moderated mediation analysis.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 139–150. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1250963.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Methodologie // methodology; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Stereotype // stereotypes; Survey // survey; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

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The Effects of Polyvictimization and Quality of Caregiver Attachment on Disclosure of Illegal Sexual Behavior.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (5), S. 625–642. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1328474.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; Psychotherapie // psychotherapy; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.5 Disclosure

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Gender Differences in the Path From Sexual Victimization to HIV Risk Behavior Among Homeless Youth.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 334–351. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1287146.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Latin@s // Latinx; Nordamerika // North America; obdachlos // homeless; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Reviktimisierung // revictimization; Risiko // risk; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Soziale Schicht // social class; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Ethnic origin of the victim as an aggravating factor in sentencing sexual offenders.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (3), S. 300–311. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1267271.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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In: *Sex Education* 17 (4), S. 386–398. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1292459.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Japan // Japan; Schule // school; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Hatchard, Christine J.; Goodwin, Jamie L.; Siddall, Eryn; Muniz, Lauren (2017):

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (4), S. 428–441. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1300971.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Frauen // women; Geschlecht // gender; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Hendry, Natalie Ann (2017):

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London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 509–526.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Soziale Medien // social media; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Hicks, Stephen; Jeyasingham, Dharman (2017):

Social Work, Queer Theory and After. A Genealogy of Sexuality Theory in Neo-Liberal Times.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2357–2373. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw103.

Schlagwörter:

queer // queer; Sexualität // sexuality; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT

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In: *Sex Education* 18 (3), S. 293–306. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2018.1431879.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Identität // identity; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Macht // power; Policies // policies; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Hlavka, Heather R. (2017):

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In: *Men and Masculinities* 20 (4), S. 482–505. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X16652656.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Jungen // boys; Macht // power; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Stigmatisierung // stigma; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Hoggart, Lesley (2017):

Internalised abortion stigma. Young women's strategies of resistance and rejection.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 27 (2), S. 186–202. DOI: 10.1177/0959353517698997.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Großbritannien // Great Britain;
junge Erwachsene // young adults; Literaturreview // literature review; qualitative Forschung // qualitative
research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schwangerschaftsabbruch // abortion; Soziale Schicht //
social class; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Hohendorff, Jean Von; Habigzang, Luísa Fernanda; Koller, Silvia Helena (2017):

"A boy, being a victim, nobody really buys that, you know?". Dynamics of sexual violence against boys.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 70, S. 53–64. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.05.008.

Schlagwörter:

Brasilien // Brazil; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht //
gender; Jungen // boys; Lateinamerika // Latin America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative
Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Hudson, Kirsty (2017):

Preventing child sexual abuse through education. The work of Stop it Now! Wales.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 24 (1), S. 99–113. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1383088.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Diskurs // discourse; Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation;
Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Methodensammlung // toolkit;
Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und
Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie;
6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Hynes, Patricia (2017):

Trafficking, Exploitation and Modern Slavery e-learning course by Virtual College, Guiseley, West Yorkshire in association with ECPAT UK and Pete Nelson, West Yorkshire Police, 2016. Available from Virtual College.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (1), S. 75–76. DOI: 10.1002/car.2465.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene // adults; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder // children; Medien // media; Menschenhandel //
human trafficking; Menschenrechte // human rights; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Policies // policies; sexueller
Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 4 Fachkräfte;
4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Children's friendships in super-diverse localities. Encounters with social and ethnic difference.

In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 128–142. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216633741.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Freunde // friends; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Grundschule // elementary school; Kinder // children; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Soziale Schicht // social class; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Javaid, Aliraza (2017):

Forgotten victims. Students' attitudes towards and responses to male sexual victimisation.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (3), S. 338–350. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1362272.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Männer // men; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Rape Culture // rape culture; Stereotype // stereotypes; Stigmatisierung // stigma; Student*innen // college students; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Jeremiah, Rohan D.; Quinn, Camille R.; Alexis, Jicinta M. (2017):

Exposing the culture of silence. Inhibiting factors in the prevention, treatment, and mitigation of sexual abuse in the Eastern Caribbean.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 66, S. 53–63. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.01.029.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Grenada // Grenada; häusliche Gewalt // domestic violence; Karibik // Caribbean; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Reviktimisierung // revictimization; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Vernachlässigung // neglect

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Jernbro, Carolina; Otterman, Gabriel; Lucas, Steven; Tindberg, Ylva; Janson, Staffan (2017):

Disclosure of Child Physical Abuse and Perceived Adult Support among Swedish Adolescents.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (6), S. 451–464. DOI: 10.1002/car.2443.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Schweden // Sweden; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

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Impact of a Romantic Relationships Counseling Group Project on Deaf Male Adolescents in a Deaf School.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (2), S. 185–206. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9481-0.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Behinderung // disability; Evaluation // evaluation; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Männer // men; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Psychotherapie // psychotherapy; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Taiwan // Taiwan

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.4 Sonderpädagogik; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Jobim Fischer, Vinicius; González-Jiménez, Antonio José (2017):

Using a comprehensive sexuality education framework to analyse the contents of a Brazilian adolescent health handbook.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (5), S. 485–497. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1308858.

Schlagwörter:

Brasilien // Brazil; Diskurs // discourse; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; international // international; Jugend // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; queer // queer; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Spanien // Spain; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Johnston, Lisa G.; Mon, Myo Myo; Steinhaus, Mara; Sass, Justine (2017):

Correlates of Forced Sex Among Young Men Who Have Sex With Men in Yangon and Monywa, Myanmar.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 1001–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0761-z.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; schwul // gay; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Survey // survey; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Jugend // youth; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Mobbing // bullying; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Literaturreview // literature review; Methodologie // methodology; Schutz // protection

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gefühle // emotions; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; pädagogische Beziehungsgestaltung // pedagogical relationship; Sexismus // sexism; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Türkei // Turkey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen

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Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; Kanada // Canada; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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Schlagwörter:

Coming out // coming out; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Familie // family; Freunde // friends; Gesundheitswesen // public health; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Sozialisation // socialization; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskurs // discourse; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Neuseeland // New Zealand; Pflegefamilie // foster care; Policies // policies; Politik // politics; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Evaluation // evaluation; Literaturreview // literature review; Policies // policies; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

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Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Internet // Internet; Kinder // children; Medien // media; Missbrauchsdarstellungen // child pornography; Pornografie // pornography; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

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Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Männer // men; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Statistiken // statistics; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Island // Iceland; Pädagogik // pedagogy; queer // queer; Schule // school; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt // violence; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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Schlagwörter:

Deutschland // Germany; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

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Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Einstellungen // attitudes; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

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Gendered pathways from child sexual abuse to sexual aggression victimization and perpetration in adolescence and young adulthood.

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Schlagwörter:

Deutschland // Germany; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Reviktimisierung // revictimization; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Krugu, John Kingsley; Mevissen, Fraukje; Münkel, Meret; Ruiters, Robert (2017):

Beyond love: a qualitative analysis of factors associated with teenage pregnancy among young women with pregnancy experience in Bolgatanga, Ghana.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (3), S. 293–307. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1216167.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Ghana // Ghana; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Tabu // taboo; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Missbrauchsdarstellungen // child pornography; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Risiko // risk; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

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In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Pädagogische Fachkräfte // pedagogical staff; Professionalität // professionalism; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017):

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In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungslücken; Literaturreview // literature review; Nordamerika // North America; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Policies // policies

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Lavie-Ajayi, Maya (2017):

"It Will Continue to Embarrass Me on Some Level, and I Think that's OK". Conceptualising Embarrassment in Discussions about Sex between Social Workers and Service Users.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2282–2299. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw116.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Israel // Israel; Pädagogische Fachkräfte // pedagogical staff; Professionalität // professionalism; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexualität // sexuality; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Tabu // taboo

Kategorien:

1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

Le Mat, Marielle L. J. (2017):

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In: *Sex Education* 17 (4), S. 413–424. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1301252.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Äthiopien // Ethiopia; Ethnographie // ethnography; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Gruppensettings // group settings; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Macht // power; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Lee, Sally; Fenge, Lee-Ann (2017):

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In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2263–2281. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw107.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Literaturreview // literature review; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Lefevre, Michelle; Hickle, Kristine; Luckock, Barry; Ruch, Gillian (2017):

Building Trust with Children and Young People at Risk of Child Sexual Exploitation. The Professional Challenge.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 47 (8), S. 2456–2473. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw181.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; pädagogische Beziehungsgestaltung // pedagogical relationship; Professionalität // professionalism; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Lemaigre, Charlotte; Taylor, Emily P.; Gittoes, Claire (2017):

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In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 70, S. 39–52. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.05.009.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Literaturreview // literature review

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Lemon, Emily; Hennink, Monique; Can Saquic, Nely Amparo (2017):

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In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (10), S. 1149–1164. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2017.1298841.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Geschlecht // gender; Grounded Theory // Grounded Theory; Guatemala // Guatemala; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Narration // narrative; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Li, Michael J.; Thing, James P.; Galvan, Frank H.; Gonzalez, Karina D.; Bluthenthal, Ricky N. (2017):

Contextualising family microaggressions and strategies of resilience among young gay and bisexual men of Latino heritage.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (1), S. 107–120. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1208273.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Homosexualität // homosexuality; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Latin@s // Latinx; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Resilienz // resilience; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.4 Resilienz

Litam, Stacey Diane A.; Bach, Jesse Edward (2017):

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (7), S. 806–817. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1360427.

Schlagwörter:

Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Internet // Internet; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; Sexuelle Ausbeutung // sexual exploitation; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Lopez, Silvia; Faro, Concepcio; Lopetegui, Lourdes; Pujol-Ribera, Enriqueta; Monteagudo, Monica; Avecilla-Palau, Angels et al. (2017):

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 246–269. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1288186.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Spanien // Spain

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Lourie, Michael A.; Needham, Belinda L. (2017):

Sexual Orientation Discordance and Young Adult Mental Health.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 943–954. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0553-8.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Identität // identity; Jugend // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Louw, Julia S. (2017):

A Qualitative Exploration of Teacher and School Staff Experiences when Teaching Sexuality Education Programmes at Special Needs Schools in South Africa.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (4), S. 425–433. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0271-8.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Behinderung // disability; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Lehrer*innen // teachers; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Südafrika // South Africa; Survey // survey; Unterricht // class

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.4 Sonderpädagogik; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Lunneblad, Johannes; Johansson, Thomas; Odenbring, Ylva (2017):

Relational trouble and student victimisation at schools. Categorisation, caring and institutionalisation.

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 25 (3), S. 389–401. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2016.1270350.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt // violence; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schweden // Sweden; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.5 Disclosure

Lynas, Jenny; Hawkins, Russell (2017):

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In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 72, S. 10–21. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.07.003.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Prävention // prevention; Schule // school; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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"I Won't Out Myself Just to Do a Survey". Sexual and Gender Minority Adolescents' Perspectives on the Risks and Benefits of Sex Research.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (5), S. 1393–1409. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0784-5.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Macapagal, Kathryn; Janssen, Erick; Matson, Margaret; Finn, Peter R.; Heiman, Julia R. (2017):

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In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (2), S. 385–394. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0679-x.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Methodologie // methodology; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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Preschoolers' disclosures of child sexual abuse. Examining corroborated cases from Swedish courts.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 70, S. 199–209. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.05.018.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children;

Schweden // Sweden; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

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Sexuality and Reproductive Health in Young People with Disability. A Systematic Review of Issues and Challenges.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (4), S. 507–516. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9505-9.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Behinderung // disability; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Indien // India; junge

Erwachsene // young adults; Literaturreview // literature review; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle

Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen;

5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 72, S. 196–205. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.08.009.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results;

Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Kinder // children; quantitative Forschung //

quantitative research; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in;

6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

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Preschool Sexuality Education?! In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

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Schlagwörter:

Kindertagesstätte // nursery; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 3 Fokus;

3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Mathews, Ben (2017):

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In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 74, S. 86–98. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.07.007.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Policies // policies; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Mathews, Ben; Bromfield, Leah; Walsh, Kerryann; Cheng, Qinglu; Norman, Rosana E. (2017):

Reports of child sexual abuse of boys and girls. Longitudinal trends over a 20-year period in Victoria, Australia.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 66, S. 9–22. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.01.025.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jungen // boys; Mädchen // girls; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Policies // policies; Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

McAllum, Mary-Anne (2017):

Young bisexual women's experiences in secondary schools. "Not everyone's straight so why are they only teaching that?"

In: *Sex Education* 18 (3), S. 253–267. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1369024.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Bisexualität // bisexuality; Einstellungen // attitudes; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungsethik // research ethics; Frauen // women; heimlicher Lehrplan // hidden curriculum; international // international; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Methodologie // methodology; Neuseeland // New Zealand; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; queer // queer; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 24 (1), S. 37–50. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1411641.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Mixed methods // mixed methods; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

McElvaney, Rosaleen; Culhane, Maebh (2017):

A Retrospective Analysis of Children's Assessment Reports. What Helps Children Tell?

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (2), S. 103–115. DOI: 10.1002/car.2390.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Europa // Europe; Irland // Ireland; Kinder // children; Methodologie // methodology; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

McGeeney, Ester (2017):

Possibilities for Pleasure. A Creative Approach to Including Pleasure in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 571–589.

Schlagwörter:

Methodensammlung // toolkit; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

McGlashan, Hayley; Fitzpatrick, Katie (2017):

'I use any pronouns, and I'm questioning everything else'. Transgender youth and the issue of gender pronouns.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (3), S. 239–252. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1419949.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Ethnographie // ethnography; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Jugend // youth; Macht // power; Neuseeland // New Zealand; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; queer // queer; Schule // school; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Identität // sexual identity; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

McGuire, Katherine; London, Kamala (2017):

Common Beliefs About Child Sexual Abuse and Disclosure. A College Sample.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 175–194. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1281368.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Einstellungen // attitudes; Erwachsene // adults; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

McHugh, Margaret T.; Kvernland, Alexandra; Palusci, Vincent J. (2017):

An Adolescent Parents' Programme to Reduce Child Abuse.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (3), S. 184–195. DOI: 10.1002/car.2426.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kinder // children; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Nordamerika // North America; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

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In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (3), S. 230–244. DOI: 10.1002/car.2452.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

McKibbin, Gemma (2017):

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In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 82, S. 373–382. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.10.008.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heim // residential care; Literaturreview // literature review; Pflegefamilie // foster care; Prävention // prevention; Prostitution // prostitution; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

McKibbin, Gemma; Humphreys, Cathy; Hamilton, Bridget (2017):

"Talking about child sexual abuse would have helped me". Young people who sexually abused reflect on preventing harmful sexual behavior.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 70, S. 210–221. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.06.017.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Kinder // children; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Meenagh, Joni (2017):

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In: *Feminism & Psychology* 27 (4), S. 447–464. DOI: 10.1177/0959353517731434.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskurs // discourse; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; junge Erwachsene // young adults; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualität // sexuality; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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The Sexual Abuse of Vulnerable People by Registered Social Workers in England. An Analysis of the Health and Care Professions Council Fitness to Practise Cases.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2190–2207. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw150.

Schlagwörter:

institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Pädagogische Fachkräfte // pedagogical staff; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Mevisen, Fraukje E. F.; van Empelen, Pepijn; Watzeels, Anita; van Duin, Gee; Meijer, Suzanne; van Lieshout, Sanne; Kok, Gerjo (2017):

Development of Long Live Love +, a school-based online sexual health programme for young adults. An intervention mapping approach.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (1), S. 47–73. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1389717.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Niederlande // Netherlands; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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The Disregarding of Heteronormativity. Emphasizing a Happy Queer Adulthood and Localizing Anti-Queer Violence to Adolescent Schools.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (3), S. 331–344. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0272-7.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Grounded Theory // Grounded Theory; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Identität // identity; lesbisch // lesbian; Medienanalyse // media analysis; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; Pubertät // Puberty; queer // queer; Resilienz // resilience; Schule // school; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.4 Resilienz

Miedema, Stephanie S.; Yount, Kathryn M.; Chirwa, Esnat; Dunkle, Kristin; Fulu, Emma (2017):

Integrating male sexual diversity into violence prevention efforts with men and boys: evidence from the Asia-Pacific Region.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (2), S. 208–224. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1214747.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Geschlecht // gender; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Gewalt // violence; Jungen // boys; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Prävention // prevention; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Statistiken // statistics

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergreif

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1269863.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Einstellungen // attitudes; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Sprache // language; USA // USA; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Miragoli, Sarah; Camisasca, Elena; Di Blasio, Paola (2017):

Child Sexual Behaviors in School Context. Age and Gender Differences.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 213–231. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280866.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Italien // Italy; Kinder // children; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Lehrer*innen // teachers; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Moore, Jeff; Thornton, Christine; Hughes, Mary (2017):

On the Road to Resilience. The Help-Seeking Experiences of Irish Emigrant Survivors of Institutional Abuse.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (5), S. 375–387. DOI: 10.1002/car.2415.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Irland // Ireland; Kinder // children; Resilienz // resilience; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Moore, Tim P.; McArthur, Morag; Noble-Carr, Debbie (2017):

More a marathon than a hurdle. Towards children's informed consent in a study on safety.

In: *Qualitative Research* 7 (2), 146879411770070. DOI: 10.1177/1468794117700708.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Ethik // ethics; Forschungsethik // research ethics; Kinder // children; Methodologie // methodology; Sicherheit // safety

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Sexing Behaviors and Cyber Pornography Addiction Among Adolescents. The Moderating Role of Alcohol Consumption.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 113–121. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0234-0.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Internet // Internet; Jugend // youth; Medien // media; Pornografie // pornography; Sexting // sexting; Soziale Medien // social media

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Morris, Matthew C.; Kouros, Chrystyna D.; Janecek, Kim; Freeman, Rachel; Mielock, Alyssa; Garber, Judy (2017):
Community-level moderators of a school-based childhood sexual assault prevention program.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 295–306. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.005.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Kinder // children; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; Sicherheit // safety; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Morton, Sarah (2017):

Getting evidence into action to tackle institutional child abuse.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 74, S. 111–114. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.10.006.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Kommentar // commentary; Policies // policies; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Sicherheit // safety

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Evaluating the One-in-Five Statistic: Women's Risk of Sexual Assault While in College.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (4-5), S. 549–576. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1295014.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Literaturreview // literature review; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Statistiken // statistics; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Mul, Nick J.; McKenzie, Cameron; Khan, Maryam (2017):

Recognition and Legitimation of Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity (SOGI) at the UN. A Critical Systemic Analysis.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2245–2262. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw139.

Schlagwörter:

Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Policies // policies; queer // queer

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Naezer, Marijke; Rommes, Els; Jansen, Willy (2017):

Empowerment through sex education? Rethinking paradoxical policies.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (6), S. 712–728. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1362633.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Empowerment // empowerment; Ethnographie // ethnography; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Literaturreview // literature review; Macht // power; Niederlande // Netherlands; Policies // policies; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Nanney, Megan; Brunnsma, David L. (2017):

Moving Beyond Cis-terhood. Determining Gender through Transgender Admittance Policies at U.S. Women's Colleges.

In: *Gender & Society* 31 (2), S. 145–170. DOI: 10.1177/0891243217690100.

Schlagwörter:

Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Geschlecht // gender; geschlechtergetrennte Bildung // single-sex education; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Identität // identity; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; queer // queer; trans*ident // trans*; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Nash, Jennifer C. (2017):

Pleasurable Blackness. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 261–278.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Schwarz // Black; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

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Spring fever. Process evaluation of a sex and relationships education programme for primary school pupils.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (1), S. 90–106. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1392297.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Grundschule // elementary school; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Newsom, Kimmery; Myers-Bowman, Karen (2017):

"I Am Not A Victim. I Am A Survivor". Resilience as a Journey for Female Survivors of Child Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (8), S. 927–947. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1360425.

Schlagwörter:

Bewältigung // coping; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Resilienz // resilience; Sexualität // sexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

Noppiari, Elina; Uusitalo, Niina; Kupiainen, Reijo (2017):

Talk to me! Possibilities of constructing children's voices in the domestic research context.

In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 68–83. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216631026.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Finnland // Finland; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Methodologie // methodology; Mixed methods // mixed methods; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Nothdurfter, Urban; Nagy, Andrea (2017):

Few and Far from Radical? LGBT-Related Contributions in European Social Work Journal Publishing.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2227–2244. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw140.

Schlagwörter:

Literaturreview // literature review; queer // queer; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK

Nyblade, Laura; Stockton, Melissa; Nyato, Daniel; Wamoyi, Joyce (2017):

Perceived, anticipated and experienced stigma. Exploring manifestations and implications for young people's sexual and reproductive health and access to care in North-Western Tanzania.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (10), S. 1092–1107. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2017.1293844.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; junge Erwachsene // young adults; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Stigmatisierung // stigma; Tansania // Tanzania

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

O'Brien, Jennifer E.; Li, Wen; Givens, Ashley; Leibowitz, George S. (2017):

Domestic minor sex trafficking among adjudicated male youth. Prevalence and links to treatment.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 82, S. 392–399. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.09.026.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Männer // men; Menschenhandel // human trafficking; Nordamerika // North America; Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; USA // USA; Vernachlässigung // neglect

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Oidtman, Jessica; Sherman, Susan G.; Morgan, Anthony; German, Danielle; Arrington-Sanders, Renata (2017):

Satisfaction and Condomless Anal Sex at Sexual Debut and Sexual Risk Among Young Black Same-Sex Attracted Men.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 947–959. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0831-2.

Schlagwörter:

erstes Mal // sexual debut; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Risiko // risk; Schwarz // Black; schwul // gay; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; USA // USA; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Ollis, Debbie (2017):

The power of feminist pedagogy in Australia. Vagina shorts and the primary prevention of violence against women.

In: *Gender and Education* 29 (4), S. 461–475. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2017.1321737.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskurs // discourse; Feminismus // feminism; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Lehrbücher // textbooks; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Pädagogik // pedagogy; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Oosten, Johanna M. F. van; Vandenbosch, Laura (2017):

Sexy online self-presentation on social network sites and the willingness to engage in sexting: A comparison of gender and age.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 54, S. 42–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.11.006.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Internet // Internet; Jugend // youth; Medien // media; Niederlande // Netherlands; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexting // sexting; Soziale Medien // social media; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Owen, Gabrielle (2017):

Adolescence, Trans Phenomena, and the Politics of Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): *The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education*.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 555–570.

Schlagwörter:

Jugend // youth; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Palmer, Donald; Feldman, Valerie (2017):

Toward a more comprehensive analysis of the role of organizational culture in child sexual abuse in institutional contexts.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 74, S. 23–34. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.08.004.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Organisation // organisation; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Parsons, Alexandria L.; Reichl, Arleigh J.; Pedersen, Cory L. (2017):

Gendered Ableism. Media Representations and Gender Role Beliefs' Effect on Perceptions of Disability and Sexuality.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (2), S. 207–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9464-6.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Erwachsene // adults; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Kanada // Canada; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexualität // sexuality; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Patell, Leigh; Saenz, Lauren P. (2017):

Immigration, Undocumented Students, and Sexuality Education in Schools. Collapsing Borders. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 327–342.

Schlagwörter:

Geflohene // refugees; Migration // migration; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Pérez-González, Alba; Guilera, Georgina; Pereda, Noemí; Jarne, Adolfo (2017):

Protective factors promoting resilience in the relation between child sexual victimization and internalizing and externalizing symptoms.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 72, S. 393–403. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.09.006.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Resilienz // resilience; Schutz // protection; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Spanien // Spain; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Peskin, Melissa F.; Markham, Christine M.; Shegog, Ross; Temple, Jeff R.; Baumler, Elizabeth R.; Addy, Robert C. et al. (2017):

Prevalence and Correlates of the Perpetration of Cyber Dating Abuse among Early Adolescents.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (2), S. 358–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0568-1.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Internet // Internet; Medien // media; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; Prävalenz // prevalence; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schüler*innen // pupils; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Peta, Christine; McKenzie, Judith; Kathard, Harsha; Africa, Adelene (2017):

We are Not Asexual Beings. Disabled Women in Zimbabwe Talk About Their Active Sexuality.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (4), S. 410–424. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0266-5.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; asexuell // asexual; Behinderung // disability; Feminismus // feminism; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Intersektionalität // intersectionality; Narration // narrative; Sexualität // sexuality; Simbabwe // Zimbabwe; Stereotype // stereotypes; Südafrika // South Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Pfaffendorf, Jessica (2017):

Sensitive Cowboys. Privileged Young Men and the Mobilization of Hybrid Masculinities in a Therapeutic Boarding School.

In: *Gender & Society* 31 (2), S. 197–222. DOI: 10.1177/0891243217694823.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnographie // ethnography; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Identität // identity; Internat // boarding school; Jugend // youth; Jungen // boys; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America; Privilegien // privilege; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Phasha, Tlakale Nareadi; Runo, Mary (2017):

Sexuality Education in Schools for Learners with Intellectual Disabilities in Kenya. Empowerment or Disempowerment?

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (3), S. 353–370. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9480-1.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Behinderung // disability; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kenia // Kenya; Lehrer*innen // teachers; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schüler*innen // pupils; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.4 Sonderpädagogik; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Porta, Carolyn M.; Gower, Amy L.; Mehus, Christopher J.; Yu, Xiaohui; Saewyc, Elizabeth M.; Eisenberg, Marla E. (2017):

"Kicked out". LGBTQ youths' bathroom experiences and preferences.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 107–112. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.005.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; international // international; Jugend // youth; Kanada // Canada; Nordamerika // North America; Peergruppe // peer group; queer // queer; Sicherheit // safety; Toiletten // bathroom; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Powell, Amber Joy; Hlavka, Heather R.; Mulla, Sameena (2017):

Intersectionality and Credibility in Child Sexual Assault Trials.

In: *Gender & Society* 31 (4), S. 457–480. DOI: 10.1177/0891243217716116.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Ethnographie // ethnography; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Geschlecht // gender; Intersektionalität // intersectionality; Kinder // children; Macht // power; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Soziale Schicht // social class; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Prock, Kristen A.; Kennedy, Angie C. (2017):

Federally-funded transitional living programs and services for LGBTQ-identified homeless youth. A profile in unmet need.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 83, S. 17–24. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.10.023.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Nordamerika // North America; obdachlos // homeless; queer // queer; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Puckett, Jae A.; Newcomb, Michael E.; Ryan, Daniel T.; Swann, Greg; Garofalo, Robert; Mustanski, Brian (2017):

Internalized Homophobia and Perceived Stigma. A Validation Study of Stigma Measures in a Sample of Young Men who Have Sex with Men.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (1), S. 1–16. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0258-5.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Homosexualität // homosexuality; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Stigmatisierung // stigma; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Qian, Linliang (2017):

“Dangerous Adolescence”. Sexuality and Disability of Institutionalized Children in a Chinese Orphanage.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (4), S. 445–459. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9511-y.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Behinderung // disability; China // China; Ethnographie // ethnography; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heim // residential care; Kinder // children; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexualität // sexuality; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Quarshie, Emmanuel Nii-Boye; Davies, Priscilla Ayebea; Badasu, Mawuena Ivanna Adzoa; Tagoe, Theophilus; Otoo, Pearl Ama; Afriyie, Patricia Opoku (2017):

Multiple perpetrator rape in Ghana. Offenders, victims and offence characteristics.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 24 (1), S. 125–141. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1378024.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Ghana // Ghana; Jugend // youth; Täter*in // offender; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Quinlivan, Kathleen (2017):

'Getting It Right'? Producing Race and Gender in the Neoliberal School Based Sexuality Education Assemblage. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): *The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education*.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 391–413.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Neuseeland // New Zealand; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Rassismus // racism; Sexualerziehung // sex ed

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Ragonese, Marisa; Bowman, Christin P.; Tolman, Deborah (2017):

Sex Education, Youth, and Advocacy. Sexual Literacy, Critical Media, and Intergenerational Sex Education(s). In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): *The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education*.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 301–325.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Medien // media; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Rawlings, Victoria (2017):

Gender Regulation, Violence and Social Hierarchies in School. 'Sluts', 'Gays' and 'Scrubs'.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan (Palgrave Studies in Gender and Education).

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Gewalt // violence; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Schule // school

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Retznik, Laura; Wienholz, Sabine; Seidel, Anja; Pantenburg, Birte; Conrad, Ines; Michel, Marion; Riedel-Heller, Steffi G. (2017):

Relationship Status Single? Young Adults with Visual, Hearing, or Physical Disability and Their Experiences with Partnership and Sexuality.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (4), S. 415–432. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9497-5.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Deutschland // Germany; erstes Mal // sexual debut; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Prävalenz // prevalence; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Chen, May S.; Ennett, Susan T. (2017):

Patterns of Dating Violence Victimization and Perpetration among Latino Youth.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (8), S. 1727–1742. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0621-0.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Latin@s // Latinx; Nordamerika // North America; Soziale Schicht // social class; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.4 Resilienz; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Richards, Christina; Bouman, Walter Pierre; Barker, Meg-John (2017):

Genderqueer and Non-Binary Genders.

London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Handbuch // handbook; queer // queer; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT

Rimer, Jonah R. (2017):

Internet sexual offending from an anthropological perspective. Analysing offender perceptions of online spaces.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 33–45. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1201158.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Missbrauchsdarstellungen // child pornography; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Rinehart, Jenny K.; Nason, Erica E.; Yeater, Elizabeth A.; Miller, Geoffrey F. (2017):

Do Some Students Need Special Protection From Research on Sex and Trauma? New Evidence for Young Adult Resilience in "Sensitive Topics" Research.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 273–283. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1156047.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsethik // research ethics; Nordamerika // North America; Resilienz // resilience; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Student*innen // college students; Trauma // trauma; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 6 Gewalt; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Robinson, Kerry H.; Davies, Cristyn (2017):

Sexuality Education in Early Childhood. In: Louisa Allen und Mary Lou Rasmussen (Hg.): The Palgrave Handbook of Sexuality Education.

London, s.l.: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 217–242.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Kinder // children; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Rogers, Vanessa (2017):

We need to talk about pornography. A resource to educate young people about the potential impact of pornography and sexualised images on relationships, body image and self-esteem.

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Schlagwörter:

Körper // body; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Pornografie // pornography; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; Sexualethik // sexual ethics

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Roodsaz, Rahil (2017):

Probing the politics of comprehensive sexuality education. 'Universality' versus 'Cultural Sensitivity': a Dutch–Bangladeshi collaboration on adolescent sexuality education.

In: *Sex Education* 18 (1), S. 107–121. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1403894.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Bangladesch // Bangladesh; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Niederlande // Netherlands; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Rossi, Erika; Poulin, François; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude (2017):

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In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 995–1008. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0571-6.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Kanada // Canada; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Røthing, Åse (2017):

Sexual orientation in Norwegian science textbooks. Heteronormativity and selective inclusion in textbooks and teaching.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 67, S. 143–151. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2017.06.005.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Inklusion // inclusion; Lehrbücher // textbooks; Medienanalyse // media analysis; Norwegen // norway; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schule // school; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Unterricht // class

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Rousseau, Ann; Beyens, Ine; Eggermont, Steven; Vandenbosch, Laura (2017):

The Dual Role of Media Internalization in Adolescent Sexual Behavior.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (6), S. 1685–1697. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0902-4.

Schlagwörter:

Belgien // Belgium; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Körper // body; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Medien // media; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Ruprah, Inder J.; Sierra, Ricardo; Sutton, Heather (2017):

Sex, violence, and drugs among Latin American and Caribbean adolescents. Do engaged parents make a difference?

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 47–56. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.10.001.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Eltern // parents; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; Gewalt // violence; Jugend // youth; Karibik // Caribbean; Kinder // children; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Sanberk, Ismail; Emen, Meltem; Kabakci, Duygu (2017):

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 288–307. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1292338.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Soziale Schicht // social class; soziale Ungleichheit // social inequality; Türkei // Turkey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Sawrikar, Pooja; Katz, Ilan (2017):

Barriers to disclosing child sexual abuse (CSA) in ethnic minority communities. A review of the literature and implications for practice in Australia.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 83, S. 302–315. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.11.011.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Australien // Australia; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Sawrikar, Pooja; Katz, Ilan (2017):

How aware of child sexual abuse (CSA) are ethnic minority communities? A literature review and suggestions for raising awareness in Australia.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 81, S. 246–260. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.08.015.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Sawrikar, Pooja; Katz, Ilan (2017):

The treatment needs of victims/survivors of child sexual abuse (CSA) from ethnic minority communities. A literature review and suggestions for practice.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 79, S. 166–179. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2017.06.021.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results;
Literaturreview // literature review; Selbstmord // suicide; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Scandurra, Leah; Khorn, Daro; Charles, Thana-Ashley; Sommer, Marni (2017):

Cambodian boys' transitions into young adulthood. Exploring the influence of societal and masculinity norms on young men's health.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (7), S. 767–780. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1259504.

Schlagwörter:

Aktionsforschung // PAR; Asien // Asia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlechterrolle // gender role;
Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Gewalt // violence; Identität // identity; junge Erwachsene // young adults;
Jungen // boys; Kambodscha // Cambodia; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; qualitative Forschung //
qualitative research; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Scarpati, Arielle Sagrillo; Pina, Afroditi (2017):

On national and cultural boundaries. A cross-cultural approach to sexual violence perpetration in Brazil and the United Kingdom.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (3), S. 312–327. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1351265.

Schlagwörter:

Brasilien // Brazil; Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results;
Großbritannien // Great Britain; international // international; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Literaturreview //
literature review; Prävalenz // prevalence; Rape Culture // rape culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence;
Sozialisation // socialization; Theorie // theory; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Schaafsma, Dilana; Kok, Gerjo; Stoffelen, Joke M. T.; Curfs, Leopold M. G. (2017):

People with Intellectual Disabilities Talk About Sexuality. Implications for the Development of Sex Education.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 21–38. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9466-4.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Intervention // intervention;
Niederlande // Netherlands; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative
interviews; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Verhütung //
contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität;
7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Schmidt, Alexander F.; Babchishin, Kelly M.; Lehmann, Robert J. B. (2017):

A Meta-Analysis of Viewing Time Measures of Sexual Interest in Children.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (1), S. 287–300. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0806-3.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Methodologie // methodology; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Séguin-Lemire, Ariane; Hébert, Martine; Cossette, Louise; Langevin, Rachel (2017):

A longitudinal study of emotion regulation among sexually abused preschoolers.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 307–316. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.11.027.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kanada // Canada; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; soziale Kompetenz // social competence; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Sellwood, Darryl; Raghavendra, Pammi; Jewell, Paul (2017):

Sexuality and Intimacy for People with Congenital Physical and Communication Disabilities. Barriers and Facilitators: A Systematic Review.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (2), S. 227–244. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-017-9474-z.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Behinderung // disability; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Intimität // intimacy; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Literaturreview // literature review; Schutz // protection; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Shannon, Barrie; Smith, Stephen J. (2017):

Dogma before diversity. The contradictory rhetoric of controversy and diversity in the politicisation of Australian queer-affirming learning materials.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (3), S. 242–255. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1302325.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Policies // policies; queer // queer; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Shepherd, Lindsay M.; Sly, Kaye F.; Girard, Jeffrey M. (2017):

Comparison of comprehensive and abstinence-only sexuality education in young African American adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 61, S. 50–63. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.09.006.

Schlagwörter:

Enthaltbarkeit // abstinence; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Schwarz // Black; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; USA // USA; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Shulman, Shmuel; Seiffge-Krenke, Inge; Walsh, Sophie D. (2017):

Is Sexual Activity During Adolescence Good for Future Romantic Relationships?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (9), S. 1867–1877. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0699-z.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Israel // Israel; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Sexualität // sexuality; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Sidebotham, Peter (2017):

Working with the Victims and Perpetrators of Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (2), S. 85–90. DOI: 10.1002/car.2467.

Schlagwörter:

Ethik // ethics; Europa // Europe; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfe // child welfare system; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Sizemore, Kayla M.; Olmstead, Spencer B. (2017):

Testing the Validity and Factor Structure of the Willingness to Engage in Consensual Non-Monogamy Scale Among College Men and Women.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 182–191. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0263-8.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Survey // survey; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017):

Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Großbritannien // Great Britain; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Mädchen // girls; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Unschuld // innocence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Spišák, Sanna; Paasonen, Susanna (2017):

Bad education? Childhood recollections of pornography, sexual exploration, learning and agency in Finland.

In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 99–112. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216646436.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Finnland // Finland; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Methodologie // methodology; Narration // narrative; Pornografie // pornography; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Unschuld // innocence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017):

Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geistliche // clergy; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Nordamerika // North America; Religion // religion; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2.9 Kirche; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Stead, Virginia (Hg.) (2017):

A guide to LGBTQ+ inclusion on campus, post-Pulse.

New York: Peter Lang (vol. 7).

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; queer // queer; soziale Unterstützung // social support; trans*ident // trans*; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule

Steine, Iris M.; Winje, Dagfinn; Skogen, Jens Christoffer; Krystal, John H.; Milde, Anne Marita; Bjorvatn, Bjørn et al. (2017):

Posttraumatic symptom profiles among adult survivors of childhood sexual abuse. A longitudinal study.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 67, S. 280–293. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.03.002.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Klinik // clinic; Norwegen // norway; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Statistiken // statistics; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Sterzing, Paul R.; Ratliff, G. Allen; Gartner, Rachel E.; McGeough, Briana L.; Johnson, Kelly C. (2017):

Social Ecological Correlates of Polyvictimization among a National Sample of Transgender, Genderqueer, and Cisgender Sexual Minority Adolescents.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 67, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.017.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Survey // survey; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Stiller, Anja; Hellmann, Deborah F. (2017):

In the aftermath of disclosing child sexual abuse. Consequences, needs, and wishes.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (3), S. 251–265. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1318964.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Deutschland // Germany; Europa // Europe; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Stone, Nicole; Ingham, Roger; McGinn, Laura; Bengry-Howell, Andrew (2017):

Talking relationships, babies and bodies with young children. The experiences of parents in England.

In: *Sex Education* 17 (5), S. 588–603. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1332988.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Gruppensettings // group settings; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Kommunikation // communication; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Storer, Heather L.; Casey, Erin A.; Herrenkohl, Todd I. (2017):

Developing “whole school” bystander interventions. The role of school-settings in influencing adolescents responses to dating violence and bullying.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 74, S. 87–95. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.01.018.

Schlagwörter:

Fokusgruppe // focus group; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Intervention // intervention; Lehrer*innen // teachers; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Strang, Emily; Peterson, Zoë D. (2017):

Unintentional Misreporting on Self-Report Measures of Sexually Aggressive Behavior. An Interview Study.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (8), S. 971–983. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1304519.

Schlagwörter:

Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Männer // men; Methodologie // methodology; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Statistiken // statistics; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Strassberg, Donald S.; Cann, Deanna; Velarde, Valerie (2017):

Sexting by High School Students.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (6), S. 1667–1672. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0926-9.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexting // sexting; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Streng, Tara K.; Kamimura, Akiko (2017):

Perceptions of University Policies to Prevent Sexual Assault on Campus Among College Students in the USA.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 133–142. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0245-x.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Nordamerika // North America; Policies // policies; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Schutzkonzept // protection concept; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Universität // college; USA // USA; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Suess-Schwend, Amets (2017):

Gender Diversity in Childhood: A Human Right.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (8), S. 2519–2520. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-017-0938-0.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Gesundheit // health; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Kinder // children; Kommentar // commentary; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Finnland // Finland; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Jugend // youth; Kinder // children; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche

Swank, Eric; Fahs, Breanne (2017):

College Students, Sexualities Identities, and Participation in Political Marches.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 122–132. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0242-0.

Schlagwörter:

Aktivismus // activism; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Identität // identity; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gesundheit // health; Japan // Japan; Literaturreview // literature review; Prävalenz // prevalence; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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Negotiating the hairless ideal in Aotearoa/New Zealand. Choice, awareness, complicity, and resistance in younger women's accounts of body hair removal.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 28 (2), S. 272–291. DOI: 10.1177/0959353517732592.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Körper // body; Neuseeland // New Zealand; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Thibodeau, Marie-Eve; Lavoie, Francine; Hébert, Martine; Blais, Martin (2017):

Childhood maltreatment and adolescent sexual risk behaviors. Unique, cumulative and interactive effects.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 72, S. 411–420. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.09.002.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kanada // Canada; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Thibodeau, Marie-Eve; Lavoie, Francine; Hébert, Martine; Blais, Martin (2017):

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In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (8), S. 994–1005. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2017.1316816.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Kanada // Canada; Kinder // children; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; Reviktimisierung // revictimization; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; Vernachlässigung // neglect

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Thomas, Roma; D'Arcy, Kate (2017):

Combatting Child Sexual Exploitation with Young People and Parents. Contributions to a Twenty-First-Century Family Support Agenda.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 47 (6), S. 1686–1703. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcx093.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; Kinder // children; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Soziale Arbeit // social work

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergreif

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Heterosexual Young Adults' Interest, Attitudes, and Experiences Related to Mixed-Gender, Multi-Person Sex.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 813–822. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0699-1.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

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In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 76, S. 192–195. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.02.037.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Heim // residential care; Macht // power; Niederlande // Netherlands; Pädagogische Fachkräfte // pedagogical staff; Peergewalt // peer violence; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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The characteristics of federal offenders sentenced for sexual exploitation of children within a large urban metropolitan region.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 181–194. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1307463.

Schlagwörter:

Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Missbrauchsdarstellungen // child pornography; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Turner, George W.; Crane, Betsy (2017):

Sexually Silenced No More, Adults with Learning Disabilities Speak Up. A Call to Action for Social Work to Frame Sexual Voice as a Social Justice Issue.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2300–2317. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw133.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Großbritannien // Great Britain; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; Soziale Arbeit // social work; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

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Sexual Inactivity During Young Adulthood Is More Common Among U.S. Millennials and iGen. Age, Period, and Cohort Effects on Having No Sexual Partners After Age 18.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (2), S. 433–440. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0798-z.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene // adults; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Statistiken // statistics; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Ullman, Jacqueline (2017):

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In: *Sex Education* 17 (3), S. 276–289. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1273104.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Lehrer*innen // teachers; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; queer // queer; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; Survey // survey; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

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Beyond exploitation. Towards a nuanced understanding of agency for adolescent female sex workers - evidence from Zanzibar and Morogoro.

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Schlagwörter:

Bewältigung // coping; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Prostitution // prostitution; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Tansania // Tanzania

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.4 Resilienz

van de Bongardt, Daphne; Reitz, Ellen; Overbeek, Geertjan; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude; Burk, Bill; Deković, Maja (2017):

Observed Normativity and Deviance in Friendship Dyads' Conversations About Sex and the Relations With Youths' Perceived Sexual Peer Norms.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (6), S. 1793–1806. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0763-x.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Freunde // friends; Geschlecht // gender; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Kommunikation // communication; Niederlande // Netherlands; Peergruppe // peer group; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

van Lisdonk, Jantine; Keuzenkamp, Saskia (2017):

Towards Bi-Inclusive Policies. Suggestions Based on Research on Dutch Same-Sex Attracted Young People.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (2), S. 206–222. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0241-1.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Niederlande // Netherlands; Policies // policies; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; queer // queer; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

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The associations of adolescents' dating violence victimization, well-being and engagement in risk behaviors.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 66–71. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.005.

Schlagwörter:

Belgien // Belgium; Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Europa // Europe; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Peergruppe // peer group; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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The associations between abuse characteristics in child sexual abuse. A meta-analysis.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 167–180. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1318963.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Literaturreview // literature review; Prävalenz // prevalence; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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A randomized controlled trial to examine the effects of the Tackling Teenage psychosexual training program for adolescents with autism spectrum disorder.

In: *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 58 (7), S. 840–850. DOI: 10.1111/jcpp.12709.

Schlagwörter:

Autismus // autism; Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Niederlande // Netherlands; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

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In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 195–212. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280576.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Eltern // parents; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Geschlecht // gender; Literaturreview // literature review; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

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The Practical Sense of Protection. A Discussion Paper on the Reporting of Child Abuse in Africa and whether International Standards Actually Help Keep Children Safe.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (4), S. 252–262. DOI: 10.1002/car.2477.

Schlagwörter:

Afrika // Africa; international // international; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Schutz // protection; Theorie // theory

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Walton, Jamie; Duff, Simon; Chou, Shihning (2017):

A Brief Discussion About Measuring Child Molester Cognition With the Sex With Children Scale.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 26 (2), S. 91–102. DOI: 10.1002/car.2361.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Methodologie // methodology; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.11 Sonstige; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Warria, Ajwang' (2017):

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In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 79, S. 274–279. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.06.024.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Heirat // marriage; international // international; Kinder // children; Literaturreview // literature review; Menschenhandel // human trafficking; Prostitution // prostitution

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in;
6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Weatherred, Jane Long (2017):

Framing Child Sexual Abuse. A Longitudinal Content Analysis of Newspaper and Television Coverage, 2002–2012.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 3–22. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1257528.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Langzeitstudie // long-term study; Medien // media; Medienanalyse // media analysis; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art;
6.2.2 Missbrauch

Weber, Sabine; Landolt, Markus A.; Maier, Thomas; Mohler-Kuo, Meichun; Schnyder, Ulrich; Jud, Andreas (2017):

Psychotherapeutic care for sexually-victimized children – Do service providers meet the need? Multilevel analysis.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 165–172. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.12.015.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Europa // Europe; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Psychotherapie // psychotherapy; Schutz // protection; Schweiz // Switzerland; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Survey // survey

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art;
6.2.2 Missbrauch

Weinsheimer, Camille C.; Woiwod, Dayna M.; Coburn, Patricia I.; Chong, Kristin; Connolly, Deborah A. (2017):

The unusual suspects. Female versus male accused in child sexual abuse cases.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 72, S. 446–455. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.09.003.

Schlagwörter:

Fallanalyse // case analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Forschungslücken; Frauen // women; Gerichtsverhandlungen // judicial proceedings; Geschlecht // gender; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Statistiken // statistics; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Wernick, Laura J.; Kulick, Alex; Chin, Matthew (2017):

Gender Identity Disparities in Bathroom Safety and Wellbeing among High School Students.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 917–930. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0652-1.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Identität // identity; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; Sicherheit // safety; Survey // survey; trans*ident // trans*; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen;
2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art;
6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Wilson, Bianca D. M.; Jordan, Sid P.; Meyer, Ilan H.; Flores, Andrew R.; Stemple, Lara; Herman, Jody L. (2017):
Disproportionality and Disparities among Sexual Minority Youth in Custody.
In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (7), S. 1547–1561. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-017-0632-5.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Winters, Georgia M.; Kaylor, Leah E.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017):

Sexual offenders contacting children online. An examination of transcripts of sexual grooming.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 62–76. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1271146.

Schlagwörter:

Grooming // grooming; Internet // Internet; Medien // media; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Wolff, Jennifer M.; Rospenda, Kathleen M.; Colaneri, Anthony S. (2017):

Sexual Harassment, Psychological Distress, and Problematic Drinking Behavior Among College Students: An Examination of Reciprocal Causal Relations.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 362–373. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1143439.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Folgen // long-term effects; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Wolowic, Jennifer M.; Heston, Laura V.; Saewyc, Elizabeth M.; Porta, Carolyn; Eisenberg, Marla E. (2017):

Chasing the rainbow: lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer youth and pride semiotics.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 19 (5), S. 557–571. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2016.1251613.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; Nordamerika // North America; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; queer // queer; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

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Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Diskursanalyse // discourse analysis; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; heimlicher Lehrplan // hidden curriculum; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Pädagogik // pedagogy; Policies // policies; Politik // politics; Prävention // prevention; qualitative Forschung //

qualitative research; Rassismus // racism; Schwarz // Black; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Theorie // theory; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Wooten, Sara Carrigan; Mitchell, Roland W. (Hg.) (2017):

Preventing sexual violence on campus. Challenging traditional approaches through program innovation.

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Schlagwörter:

Policies // policies; Prävention // prevention; Rape Culture // rape culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Universität // college

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

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The Roles of Politics, Feminism, and Religion in Attitudes Toward LGBT Individuals. A Cross-Cultural Study of College Students in the USA, Italy, and Spain.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (3), S. 241–258. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-016-0244-y.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Feminismus // feminism; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; international // international; Italien // Italy; Nordamerika // North America; Politik // politics; queer // queer; Spanien // Spain; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; Universität // college; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

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In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 74, S. 10–22. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.08.028.

Schlagwörter:

Aufdeckung // disclosure; Australien // Australia; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschichte // history; Großbritannien // Great Britain; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; international // international; Irland // Ireland

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Yıldız, Gizem; Cavkaytar, Atilla (2017):

Effectiveness of a Sexual Education Program for Mothers of Young Adults with Intellectual Disabilities on Mothers' Attitudes Toward Sexual Education and the Perception of Social Support.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 3–19. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9465-5.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Behinderung // disability; Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Evaluation // evaluation; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; junge Erwachsene // young adults; Methodensammlung // toolkit; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Türkei // Turkey

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Yoder, Jamie R.; Dillard, Rebecca; Stehlik, Lorraine (2017):

Disparate reports of stress and family relations between youth who commit sexual crimes and their caregivers.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 24 (1), S. 114–124. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1372938.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Jugend // youth; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Nordamerika // North America; quantitative Forschung // quantitative research; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Pädagogische FK; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Youatt, Emily J.; Harris, Lisa H.; Harper, Gary W.; Janz, Nancy K.; Bauermeister, José A. (2017):

Sexual Health Care Services among Young Adult Sexual Minority Women.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 14 (3), S. 345–357. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-017-0277-x.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Coming out // coming out; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Frauen // women; Gesundheit // health; Homosexualität // homosexuality; junge Erwachsene // young adults; lesbisch // lesbian; Nordamerika // North America; queer // queer; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Zalcborg, Sara (2017):

The Place of Culture and Religion in Patterns of Disclosure and Reporting Sexual Abuse of Males. A Case Study of Ultra Orthodox Male Victims.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (5), S. 590–607. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1316335.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Aufdeckung // disclosure; Familie // family; Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Geschlecht // gender; Israel // Israel; Jugend // youth; Jungen // boys; Männer // men; qualitative Forschung // qualitative research; qualitative Interviews // qualitative interviews; Religion // religion; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch // child sexual abuse

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Zamboni, Brian; Bezek, Katelyn (2017):

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In: *Sex Education* 17 (4), S. 371–385. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2017.1299703.

Schlagwörter:

Forschungsergebnisse // research results; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Student*innen // college students; Survey // survey; USA // USA

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern

Beiträge sortiert nach Kategorien

1. Sozialer Kontext

1.1. Policies

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Alkhalileh, Duna; Hayford, Sarah R.; Norris, Alison H.; Gallo, Maria F. (2018): Prevalence and attitudes on female genital mutilation/cutting in Egypt since criminalisation in 2008. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 20 (2), S. 173–182. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2017.1337927.

Allroggen, Marc; Rau, Thea; Ohlert, Jeannine; Fegert, Jörg M. (2017): Lifetime prevalence and incidence of sexual victimization of adolescents in institutional care. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 66, S. 23–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.015.

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2. Institutioneller Kontext

2.1. Dynamiken

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3.2. Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

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6. Gewalt

6.1. Täter*in

6.1.1. Peer

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6.2. Art

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6.2.5. Diskriminierung

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6.5. Disclosure

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7. Sexualität

7.1. Beziehungsgestaltung

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